

SATISFACTORY

Project Acronym: **SatisFactory**
 Project Full Title: **A collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing satisfaction and working experience in smart factory environments**
 Grant Agreement: **636302**
 Project Duration: **36 months (01/01/2015 - 31/12/2017)**

DELIVERABLE D1.1

User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines

Deliverable Status: **Final**
 File Name: **Satisfactory-Deliverable-D1.1_v3.pdf**
 Due Date: **February 2017 (M26)**
 Submission Date: **February 2017 (M26)**
 Task Leader: **COMAU**

Dissemination level	
Public	X
Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement n°636302

The SatisFactory project consortium is composed of:		
CERTH¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA²	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FIT	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
SUNLIGHT	Systems Sunlight Industrial & Commercial Company of Defensive, Energy, Electronic and Telecommunication Systems S.A.	Greece
GlassUP	GlassUp srl	Italy
QPLAN	Q-PLAN International Advisors LTD	Greece

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

¹ Project Coordinator

² Terminated beneficiary since June 2016 and replaced by QPLAN

AUTHORS LIST

Leading Author (Editor)				
Surname		First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
Cultrona		Pietro Alberto	COMAU	Pietro.cultrona@comau.com
Co-authors (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Brizzi	Paolo	ISMB	brizzi@ismb.it
2	Elmasllari	Erion	Frahofer FIT	erion.elmasllari@fit.fraunhofer.de
3	Elsianli	Katerina	ABE	elsianli@abe.gr
4	Ippolito	Massimo	COMAU	MASSIMO.IPPOLITO@comau.com
5	Jentsch	Marc	Frahofer FIT	marc.jentsch@fit.fraunhofer.de
6	Kanidis	Stefanos	SUNLIGHT	s.kanidis@sunlight.gr
7	Krinidis	Stelios	CERTH	krinidis@iti.gr
8	Matiouk	Svetlana	Frahofer FIT	svetlana.matiouk@fit.fraunhofer.de
9	Mautino	Sara	GlassUP	sara@glassup.net
10	Metaxa	Ifigeneia	ABE	metaxa@abe.gr
11	Parcharidis	Symeon	SUNLIGHT	s.parcharidis@sunlight.gr
12	Putero	Michele	COMAU	michele.putero@comau.com
13	Rusinà	Fulvio	COMAU	Fulvio.rusina@comau.com
14	Tsolakis	Apostolos	CERTH	tsolakis@iti.gr
15	Turinetto	Maurizio	Regola	m.turinetto@regola.it
16	Voutetakis	Spyros	CERTH	paris@cperi.certh.gr
17	Zikos	Stylios	CERTH	szikos@iti.gr
18	Ziougou	Chrysovalantou	CERTH	cziougou@cperi.certh.gr

REVIEWERS LIST

List of Reviewers (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Dos Santos	Stephanie	SIGMA	stephanie.dos-santos@sigma-orionis.com
2	Ioannidis	Dimos	CERTH	djoannid@iti.gr
3	Ziazios	Constantinos	ABE	ziazios@abe.gr

REVISION CONTROL

Version	Author	Date	Status
0.1	COMAU	January, 2015	Initial Draft
0.2	FIT	January, 2015	ToC Revision
0.3	COMAU	January, 2015	ToC Update, preliminary interviews template
0.4	ABE	February, 2015	Added section on legislation and initial use-case template
0.5	FIT	April, 2015	Requirements engineering structure and description of users and stakeholders for SUNLIGHT and CERTH
0.6	COMAU	April, 2015	COMAU Interviews
0.7	COMAU	April, 2015	COMAU context of use and preliminary analysis of stakeholders interviews
0.8	CERTH	April, 2015	CERTH context of use and preliminary analysis of stakeholders interviews
0.9	REGOLA, ISMB, GlassUP, Sunlight	April, 2015	Tech. requirements; Sunlight context of use and preliminary analysis of stakeholders interviews
1.0	COMAU/ CERTH	April, 2015	Ready for submission to the EC
1.1	COMAU	January, 2016	ToC updated and Jira Issues analysis added
1.2	FIT	January, 2016	Approach & Methodology sections updated
1.3	ATLANTIS	February, 2016	Context of use & analysis - Maintenance section updated
1.4	Sunlight	February, 2016	Update SUNLIGHT use-cases
2.0	COMAU/ CERTH	February, 2016	Ready for submission to the EC
2.2	COMAU	February, 2017	First Draft of 3 rd version available
2.8	ALL	February, 2017	Minor changes from all partners
3.0	COMAU/ CERTH	February, 2017	Ready for submission to the EC

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of Figures	8
List of Definitions & Abbreviations	11
Executive Summary	13
1. Introduction.....	15
1.1 Purpose, Context and Scope of this Deliverable.....	15
1.2 Background	16
2. Approach & methodology	18
2.1 Human-centered design process	18
2.1.1 General ISO 9241-210 process model	18
2.2 Methods for context of use research.....	19
2.2.1 Context of use definition	19
2.2.2 Analytic methods	21
2.2.3 Ethnographic methods.....	21
2.2.4 Research through design.....	22
2.3 SatisFactory requirements engineering approach	23
2.3.1 Volere requirements approach	23
2.3.2 Requirements in the SatisFactory design process	36
2.3.3 Online support for requirements in SatisFactory	37
2.4 Progress beyond first document iteration	41
2.4.1 Approach.....	41
2.4.2 Methodology.....	41
2.4.3 Lessons learned.....	42
2.4.4 Jira Platform.....	44
3. Context of use analysis	46
3.1 Production processes, actors and stakeholders.....	46
3.1.1 Production processes	46
3.1.2 Actors and Stakeholders.....	46
3.2 Description of the context of use	48
3.2.1 COMAU – Automotive discrete manufacturing	48
3.2.2 CERTH/CPERI – Chemical continuous process	60
3.2.3 SUNLIGHT – Batteries discrete manufacturing.....	69
3.2.4 ATLANTIS – Maintenance operations.....	77
4. End-users requirements analysis.....	79
4.1 Requirements collection process.....	79
4.2 Requirements analysis	80
4.2.1 COMAU - Automotive discrete manufacturing	80
4.2.2 CERTH – Chemical continuous process.....	87
4.2.3 SUNLIGHT – Batteries discrete manufacturing.....	93
4.2.4 Interviews Report	99
5. Key topics and Requirements	102
5.1 End-users Key topics.....	102
5.1.1 Key topics from Comau interview process	102

5.1.2	Key topics from CERTH/CPERI interview process	104
5.1.3	Key topics from Sunlight interview process	104
5.2	REQUIREMENTS AND USER NEEDS	106
5.3	Overall activity on Jira issues	106
5.4	Jira issues detailed analysis	107
6.	Conclusions	116
	References	117
	Annex 1 – Interview notes and template.....	119
	Annex 2 – Requirements template (Volere).....	123
	Annex 3 – Legislation review	124
	Annex 4 – Workplaces ergonomics.....	132
	Annex 5 – Informed Consent For Interviews	139
	Annex 6 – Issues from Jira Database	146

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: ISO9241-210 Process Model.....19

Figure 2: Overview of the Context of Use 21

Figure 3: The Volere “Requirements Shell” for representing so-called atomic requirements. 25

Figure 4: Overview of the Volere Process Model..... 26

Figure 5: Syntax for formulating user needs 27

Figure 6: Iterative human-centred design approach36

Figure 7: Syntax for formulating requirements for use..... 37

Figure 8: Screenshot of the user need creation dialog in SatisFactory38

Figure 9: “Mandatory” part of the Volere Requirement creation dialog 39

Figure 10: “Supporting entries” part of the Volere Requirement creation dialog 39

Figure 11: State diagram of issue type “User Need”40

Figure 12: State diagram of issue type “Volere Requirement”40

Figure 13: End-users test-beds reference model 46

Figure 14: Categorization of Actors and Stakeholders47

Figure 15: Categorization of Internal Stakeholders and Connected Stakeholders..... 47

Figure 16: COMAU Smart5 NJ4-90 hollow wrist robot..... 48

Figure 17: COMAU robot hollow wrist 49

Figure 18: COMAU Smart5 NJ4-90 with COMAU Compact welding gun50

Figure 19: COMAU Compact welding gun 50

Figure 20: COMAU body-welding line 51

Figure 21: COMAU body-side fixtures..... 51

Figure 22: Process Operators during piping installation on a robot arm.....52

Figure 23: COMAU NJ4 90 in new, grey outfit..... 57

Figure 24: COMAU NJ 110 / 130 in new, grey outfit 57

Figure 25: COMAU AURA (Advanced Use Robotic Arm)..... 58

Figure 26: COMAU Amico at EMO MILANO 2015 Fair58

Figure 27: Partial overview of CERTH/CPERIs shop floor and plants 61

Figure 28: CERTH/CPERI’s Monitoring and control HMIs 61

Figure 29: Process Overview 62

Figure 30: Process Flow diagram of the Continuous Pilot Plant 63

Figure 31: Knowledge sharing from the signal data to actionable knowledge..... 64

Figure 32: Jar formation..... 69

Figure 33: Sunlight Motive Power Battery 70

Figure 34: Sunlight Motive Power Battery Assembly line.....	71
Figure 35: OPzS & OPzV Manual Assembly line	72
Figure 36: COMAU stakeholders applications & roles.....	81
Figure 37: COMAU actors and stakeholders' education level	81
Figure 38: COMAU stakeholders years of experience in the role.....	82
Figure 39: COMAU Technological areas of expertise	82
Figure 40: How COMAU actors came to this job	83
Figure 41: Personal Protective Equipment (OSHA classification).....	84
Figure 42: COMAU actors' workplace	84
Figure 43: Personnel Turnover.....	85
Figure 44: Personnel wished training.....	86
Figure 45: Overall Workplace satisfaction degree	86
Figure 46: CERTH actors' categories.....	87
Figure 47: CERTH actors' years of experience	88
Figure 48: CERTH actors' education level	88
Figure 49: CERTH actors' areas of expertise	89
Figure 50: How CERTH actors came to this job	89
Figure 51: CERTH actors' workplace	90
Figure 52: CERTH actors' safety equipment usage	91
Figure 53: CERTH actors' turnover.....	91
Figure 54: CERTH actors' wished training	92
Figure 55: CERTH actors' overall workplace satisfaction degree	93
Figure 56: Sunlight actors' categories.....	94
Figure 57: Sunlight actors' years of experience	94
Figure 58: Sunlight actors' education	95
Figure 59: Sunlight actors' areas of expertise	95
Figure 60: How Sunlight actors' found this job	96
Figure 61: SUNLIGHT actors' workplace.....	96
Figure 62: Sunlight actors' safety equipment usage	97
Figure 63: Sunlight actors' turnover.....	98
Figure 64: Sunlight actors' wished training.....	98
Figure 65: Sunlight overall workplace satisfaction degree	99
Figure 66: SUNLIGHT User Selection w.r.t. Job Description	100
Figure 67: SUNLIGHT User Selection w.r.t. Department	100
Figure 68: SUNLIGHT User Selection w.r.t. Work Experience (Years).....	101
Figure 69: Total Issues per Assignee	107

Figure 70: Total Issues grouped by type.....108
Figure 71: Total Issues grouped by priority level109
Figure 72: Total Issues grouped by status 110
Figure 73: Frequency of labels assigned to database entries 111
Figure 74: Total Issues per Creator..... 113
Figure 75: Total Requirements grouped by type 114

LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
APAC	Asia-Pacific
AR	Augmented Reality
BW	Body Welding
DG RTD	Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
ICT	Information & Communications Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MLD	Multi-Layered Description
OPC	OLE (Object Linking and Embedding) for Process Control
OP-MLD	Operating Procedures Multi-Layered Description
PC	Personal Computer
R&D	Research & Development
RFID	Radio-frequency identification
SCADA	Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition
SMLC	Smart Manufacturing Leadership Coalition
SOTA	State-Of-The-Art
UWB	Ultra Wideband Technology
WCM	World Class Manufacturing

WP	Workpackage
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020), reporting the results of the activities carried out by WP1.

SatisFactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies in ways that are both productive and appealing to youth.

For this aim, WP1 will manage and undertake the work in carrying out the iterative engineering of requirements, which special focuses on the engineering process of initial requirements and reengineering after the end of each iteration cycle.

The purpose of this WorkPackage is thus to maintain a continuous discovery and analysis of user centric requirements, needs and prospects, to be used in the design, development, implementation and validation of the SatisFactory platform and services.

The main objective of this deliverable is to describe the requirements of the prototype applications for the three end-users test-beds: discrete manufacturing in automotive, discrete manufacturing for batteries and continuous process in chemical applications. Specifically, the goal of this document is to define the list of SatisFactory requirements exploiting the "Volere" approach, that will be continuously updated and refined through an iterative process that will lead to the production of a total of three releases of this document, respectively in Project Months M4, M14 and M26. Each version of the deliverable is a self-contained document, so as the reader will not be forced to read the previous versions.

In particular, it is worth to highlight that the collection of requirements, performed through more than 40 face-to-face interviews of end-user employees, followed by brainstorming sessions among technology partners, provided in the first iteration more than 83 requirements, that became 227 during the first project year and of these 89 passed the quality check and became part of the Annex in the second iteration of the document. Following key requirement areas are provided:

- Manufacturing process monitoring & verification
- Production & maintenance documents access and guidelines
- Workload planning
- Training procedures
- Safety, ergonomics & privacy
- Communication, IoT and smart sensing
- Gestures recognition and vocal interaction
- Middleware & platform

These topics will be the main areas of improvement that the SatisFactory project will consider during the future development phases performed in the technical WorkPackages and validated through an iterative process.

This deliverable, after the introductory chapter, presents in Chapter 2 the requirements engineering approach and the Volere methodology adopted, giving details on the web-portal used to maintain the requirements database.

The following, Chapter 3, depicts the production processes, as well as the actors and stakeholders considered in the SatisFactory project. The first section gives the main definitions, while the second one introduces details of the considered manufacturing processes with the associated workers involved for each domain.

In Chapter 4, the process adopted to collect the user requirements and the main results of the interviews performed are presented. This activity was conducted through face-to-face interviews in the premises of the three considered industrial sectors.

Finally, the key messages extracted from each end-user, including their transposition in the Volere Requirements template, are described Chapter 5.

During the third iteration of the document above described chapters have not been modified or somehow altered for what concerns main subject and focus; they have just been smoothly updated to reflect the evolving situation, accordingly to the continuous improvement and continuous shopfloor validation approach characterizing the whole project.

By so, paragraphs of chapter 2 – Approach & methodology (especially subchapter 2.4.4 – Jira Platform) have been updated accordingly to progresses made on JIRA requirements collection and management system. Same revision lead to overall alignment of almost whole chapter 5 – Key topics and Requirements (paragraphs 5.2 – REQUIREMENTS AND USER NEEDS, 5.3 – Overall activity on Jira issues and 5.4 – Jira issues detailed analysis).

Finally, some changes have been introduced into COMAU use cases, introducing some changes into scope and considered environment / scenario. Chapter 3.2 – Description of the context of use have been updated accordingly and a specific contribution (paragraph 3.2.1.4 – Further Progresses Achieved with Third and Last Iteration onto COMAU Use-Cases) has been added to subchapter 3.2.1 – COMAU – Automotive discrete manufacturing, devoted to the industrial partner.

1. INTRODUCTION

SatisFactory aims to contribute to the transformation of traditional industrial environments using cutting-edge technologies in ways that are both productive and appealing to youth.

The fundamental component of the proposed system will be the assessment and storage of the explicit and tacit knowledge created on the shop floor by aggregating a set of heterogeneous smart devices and sensors and extracting context-aware information based on their measurements. The distribution of this knowledge will be based on 3 important system tools: a training platform to allow the fast and intuitive education of employees; a collaboration platform, to stimulate and promote team interactions; ubiquitous user interfaces to support all employees seamlessly in real time and on the move.

SatisFactory will also utilize the aggregated knowledge in order to leverage the control and re-adaptation of facilities and streamline the workload. In order to enhance working experience and thus increase the workplace attractiveness, augmented reality and gamification approaches will be utilized. Additionally modern wearable devices will allow the interaction of workers with the system without disrupting their workflow. Validation will assess the impact and reveal the capabilities of SatisFactory towards the promotion of novel and viable business models for increased innovation potential, flexibility and productivity, while enhancing workplace attractiveness.

1.1 *PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE*

The purpose of this deliverable is to give a systematic formalization of a set of relevant specifications, necessary to the development of the prototype application. This document describes the method to support user requirements analysis adapting it to the different environments involved in the SatisFactory project and providing a full overview about the requirements.

These requirements will guide the development phases within the technical work packages, and therefore, this deliverable will be the first common source of user requirements for the SatisFactory consortium. The list of requirements in this document reflects the work performed in Tasks T1.1 – “End-user and shop floor, system requirements and specifications”, T1.3 – “Use Cases and Scenarios” and T1.5 – “Guidelines for Deployment”, and emerged from the interview process conducted with representatives from the three application domains of the SatisFactory project: discrete manufacturing in automotive, discrete manufacturing for batteries and continuous process in chemical applications.

Specifically, the goal of the deliverable is to define a list of requirements exploiting the “Volere” approach, that will be continuously updated and refined through an iterative process that will lead to the production of a total of three releases of this document, respectively in Project Months M4, M14 and M26.

The development of this deliverable was coordinated by COMAU with contribution of CERTH / CPERI, SUNLIGHT, ABE-ATLANTIS, FRAUNHOFER FIT, ISMB, REGOLA and GLASSUP.

1.2 BACKGROUND

This deliverable belongs to WP₁ - Domain Analysis and Requirements Engineering, which is dedicated to the definition of the requirements for a safer and more attractive shop-floor environment and the guidelines and recommendations for design and deployment of SatisFactory applications in end-users test-beds. Within the Work Package, more specifically, tasks T1.1 and T1.3 are focused on development of user and system requirements according to the use case and scenarios analysed in the project, while task T1.5 intends to study the needs and requirements that should be fulfilled to guarantee successful deployment of the technologies developed in the SatisFactory project.

Manufacturing is a key enabler for European societal challenges, to this aim, the EFFRA association (European Factories of the Future Research Association), developed a multi-annual roadmap (EFFRA 2013), to guide the manufacturing research programs that will lead to more innovative manufacturing approaches.

Europe is heavily investing in maintaining its manufacturing excellence nowadays, facing the high level of competitiveness of APAC countries from one side and the recent revamping of the US manufacturing from the other.

The Horizon 2020 program strategy emphasises the need for organising and designing manufacturing in a way which ensures that manufacturing enterprises will remain socially sustainable while still achieving global competitiveness. To resolve these issues, interdisciplinary research and innovation is needed to provide the basis for the design of adequate manufacturing environments and workplaces. As a result, human capability and machine intelligence will be integrated within production systems that can achieve maximum efficiency as well as worker satisfaction. Research efforts should tackle social sustainability challenges at all levels of manufacturing industries. This effort will be economically very successful, while still improving corporate social responsibility, inclusive workplace design, and efficient use of ICT to leverage the competence of the European workforce.

Increasing complexity of manufacturing systems and processes creates the need for knowledge-workers to be supported by appropriate tools providing them with assistance for operations along the entire production chain in factories and further development of their competences. There is a clear need to contextualise from complex documentation. Appropriate interfaces (e.g. visual, audio, etc.) and assistance tools for knowledge communication will assist workers while performing manufacturing operations, including assembly, operation of machines, maintenance activities, ramp-up procedures, troubleshooting and remote guidance. Advanced human-machine interfaces for workers are required, considering:

- usability and the related learning process;
- physical, sensorial and cognitive interaction; and
- fulfilment of safety and health conditions during human-machine interaction.

The expected, extensive collaboration between future knowledge-workers and robots (as well as other advanced automation equipment) will be crucial for successful human-centred design.

ICT can play a pivotal role in making manufacturing more attractive through the development of tools and methodologies, such as serious games, demonstrators and social networks that engage the potential workforce from an early stage. Procedures to identify and reinforce the capacity of workers to remain motivated during their working day need also to be investigated. Furthermore, ICT could give more engagement opportunities such as product design and app development to the

younger generation who are already technology savvy and adept at problem solving through programming in the mobile environment. Future ICT research should develop metrics and feedback mechanisms to understand the impact on younger generations.

After EFFRA, also other associations have focused the industry innovation, in particular the German industry has developed a reference framework named Industrie 4.0 (hightech-strategie.de) with the main goal of preparing the German industry for the next industrial revolution. Priorities of this program are the Horizontal and vertical system integration, Normalisation and standardization, Logistics and finally Labour and organisation. This last point includes aspects such as workers safety and satisfaction, as well as innovative workplace design, "since good jobs are an important basis for creative ideas and economic innovation"

In parallel to EFFRA and Industrie 4.0 activities, in USA the SMLC Smart Manufacturing Leadership Coalition, is targeting the innovation activities in US manufacturing. Main priorities of this industry coalition are Additive manufacturing, Lightweight and modern metals, Next generation power electronics as well as Digital manufacturing & design, with the main scope of promoting 'American-made' and retaining jobs.

2. APPROACH & METHODOLOGY

2.1 HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN PROCESS

In order for Satisfactory to fulfil its goals, it needs to closely communicate, be guided from, and be led from the people on the factory floor. They are the target of our project, and at the same time the key to understanding how their work life can be improved and how others can be inspired to work in factories. In this environment, the best approach is User Centered Design. Its characteristics are:

- the design is based upon an explicit understanding of users, tasks and environments
- users are involved throughout design and development
- the design is driven and refined by user evaluations
- the process is iterative
- the design addresses the whole user experience
- the design team includes multidisciplinary skills and perspectives

The approach is rooted on domain analysis and interaction with the workers and other stakeholders. Design and development follows from the insights acquired during domain analysis, in an iterative manner. They grow from simple, paper-based sketches, to prototypes, and to final products. As a crucial step in every iteration, prototypes and concepts are evaluated by users to check that they progress in the right course towards fulfilling the users' needs and the project's aims.

2.1.1 General ISO 9241-210 process model

In the words of the ISO 9241-210 Standard:

Using a human-centred approach to design and development has substantial economic and social benefits for users, employers and suppliers. Highly usable systems and products tend to be more successful both technically and commercially.

The process model introduced by ISO 9241-210 for Human Centered Design is depicted in Figure 1:

Figure 1: ISO9241-210 Process Model

In this process model, work starts with understanding the context of use, i.e. the users, tools, tasks, social and physical environments where the developed system will be used and whose needs it will fulfil. (See also Section 2.2.1).

Once some (partial) understanding of the context has been reached, requirements are derived from it. These, especially in the beginning, take the form of user requirements, i.e. what the user needs from the system. Only in a later iteration, when the system starts to take a concrete shape, are these requirements transformed into system requirements, i.e. what the system must offer or how the architecture should look like.

Based on requirements, a prototype of the system is created in the third step. This can be as simple as a paper prototype or scenario for the first iterations, or as complex as a beta-version of the software in the later iterations. The prototype is, however, not a goal in itself, but only a tool that allows us to verify -- evaluate -- with the users, whether we have understood correctly what they need. The prototype is, in a sense, an embodiment of our understanding of the context. The evaluation usually yields new knowledge about the context, points out things that were forgotten or underestimated, as well as approaches that seem to work. Based on this, the picture of the context is corrected, widened, or better defined, and the cycle starts anew.

2.2 METHODS FOR CONTEXT OF USE RESEARCH

2.2.1 Context of use definition

The data describing the Context of Use can be organised according to the four major categories: i) Users, ii) their tasks and goals, iii) tools and environment, iv) workflows as well as organisational and social surroundings.

Insights on factors influencing work satisfaction of the shop-floor workers could be related to any of these categories, since the entire context of use (or in the case of SatisFactory we could say "context of work") is important for a pleasant working experience. Thus, it is suggested to highlight the key factors that – based on the ethnographic data gathered during the user research, e.g. interviews and observations – are especially contributing to satisfaction of the workers.

In the following some examples for the types of data for each category are given.

2.2.1.1 **Users**

- Skills, expertise, competence
- Pre-knowledge and –experience
- Roles and Education
- Motoric and sensory abilities
- Expectations of the technology: Content, functionality, design

2.2.1.2 **Tasks and goals**

- Activities targeted at the achievement of a goal
- Considering frequency and duration
- Goals and motivation of the user, provider, supplier, vendor
- Business and marketing goals

2.2.1.3 **Tools and environment**

- Surrounding conditions (hardware, software, equipment,...)
- Environment of use (office, home, mobile, ...)
- Competitors

2.2.1.4 **Workflows, Organizational and social surrounding**

- Work processes
- Current legislation
- Law of nature
- Instructions / Regulations / Standards / Best Practices
- Corporate culture

Figure 2: Overview of the Context of Use

2.2.2 Analytic methods

2.2.2.1 Literature research

The central question of Satisfactory is, in essence, the same question that Human Resources Management Science has been asking itself for many years: How to motivate people and improve their satisfaction? The Satisfactory approach, however, looks at this question from the technological support point of view. It is very useful to look at other approaches, both technological and otherwise, in order to learn from them. Literature research is the best method to achieve this goal and will provide us with a frame within which the Satisfactory tools and systems have to exist.

2.2.2.2 Document analysis

Work processes, environments, and rules are described and regulated in highly detailed ways. Some of this is defined by legal frameworks, other parts by company-internal regulations. There is, in essence, a very rigid frame within which Satisfactory artefacts and solutions have to work. For that very reason, document analysis -- regulations, rules, job descriptions, HR reports, and any other relevant data must be studied and used to understand the frame as well as to find out what opportunities and support it can also offer to the project. Document analysis should be used only in conjunction with ethnographic methods (Section 2.2.3), because they typically present a wished-for state, but not the way work is done in the real world.

2.2.3 Ethnographic methods

By examining how people actually communicate and work together, the ethnographic approach enables us to understand how people face the daily challenges at work, what they consider as normal, what they see as positive, and what is tiring and problematic and should be changed. The aim is to reveal ways in which collaboration is done practically, as well as "holes" and socio-physical structures which a technology approach can fill and support accordingly.

2.2.3.1 *Interviews*

'Insider accounts' from people who work in factories can provide critical insight into what makes them work at a factory, what motivates them, and what needs to be improved. A range of interviewing techniques will be used:

Semi-structured interviews utilise a prepared list of questions, based on literature review, existing domain and problem knowledge, etc. However, it is allowed to stray from the plan if the conversation leads into interesting areas that were not anticipated in the list. The main point is to watch out for interesting remarks and follow up with new, on-the-spot questions to probe deeper.

Ethnographic interviews combine observation and questions, to gain insight into environmental contexts, communication and practice of the job. The idea is to interview users in their settings, possibly while they are performing tasks, asking questions about what they are doing, how they do things and why along the way, or asking them to think out loud and perform walk-throughs of their job with the researchers.

2.2.3.2 *Observations*

It is easy to read how work should be done by the book. However, to really understand how it is done in practice, observation is crucial. People often stray from the rules of the book; it is said that the most effective way to strike is to do everything by the book: Work will simply stop because the rules don't foresee every possible situation.

Ethnographic studies of work practices have been used very effectively to inform IT systems design (e.g. Button 2000; Heath et al. 2010; Suchman 1997). Such studies do not simply generate requirements, but rather represent an enquiry which supports further design and discussions with stakeholders.

2.2.3.3 *Participant observation*

Participant observation consists of following and observing workers' activities attentively, with a focus on how they interact with the social and material worlds around them, with environments, technologies, artefacts and materials. Researchers should simply follow activities as they happen.

2.2.4 *Research through design*

2.2.4.1 *Scenarios*

Scenarios are a free form narrative that tells the existing practices as well as future visions of a product or system being developed. Scenarios normally do not explain the details of the interaction or the system; they are purposefully left rough and vague in order to avoid users hanging onto details and overlooking the general issue of whether the vision expressed by the scenario fits in their world and fulfils their needs.

2.2.4.2 *Co-Design*

User-centered design puts the user in focus, but allows design to happen in a lab, far from the place of use. While easier to carry out, design in a lab has been shown to be problematic, because the rest

of the context cannot be completely transplanted into the lab environment. The ways in which people appropriate and use technologies are highly dependent on what's available in their environment. In co-design, the distinction between users, designers, and researchers blurs, and they all work together, in place, to design a working solution that fits the context of use and the needs of the users.

2.2.4.3 *Prototyping*

Prototypes put something concrete in front of the stakeholders, so that all discussion can be done at the same level and towards a concrete, possible implementation of the system. It is important for prototypes to be visibly unfinished, so people don't waste time discussing about unimportant details but rather about the important general concepts.

2.3 *SATISFACTORY REQUIREMENTS ENGINEERING APPROACH*

SatisFactory is using the Volere Requirements approach described in (Robertson and Robertson 1999; Robertson and Robertson 2004; Robertson and Robertson 2010). Volere is a proven and widely used general-purpose approach to requirements elicitation, including both the process of eliciting requirements as well as the format for representing them. Section 2.3.1 provides an overview of key elements of the Volere approach. In particular, subsection 2.3.1.3 provides descriptions of the content and motivation for the 33 Volere requirement types being used in SatisFactory. These descriptions serve as reference for understanding the SatisFactory requirements given in Chapter 5 - Key topics and Requirements.

To suit the particular needs of an international research project, SatisFactory has integrated adapted elements of the Volere approach into the SatisFactory design approach. Relevant details on this adaptation and integration are described in sections 2.3.2 and 2.3.3.

2.3.1 *Volere requirements approach*

The Volere requirements approach is described in (Robertson and Robertson 1999; Robertson and Robertson 2004) There is also a web-site dedicated to the Volere approach here:

<http://www.volere.co.uk/>

One of the various resources available on this site is the so-called "Volere Requirements Specification Template" (Robertson and Robertson 2010).

Moreover, there is a very active community around the Volere approach on LinkedIn:

<http://www.linkedin.com/groups/Volere-Requirements-2491512>

This community is highly valuable for obtaining practical guidance for applying the Volere approach and for requirements elicitation in general.

The Volere approach defines 27 sections for the requirements specification, as presented in 2.3.1.3. Each of these sections contains one or more subsection. Altogether Volere defines almost 100 subsections for a complete Volere requirements specification. Out of these, 33 subsections correspond to different types of requirements. The other subsections of the specification correspond to other, auxiliary information, such as use-cases.

The 33 requirement types share the same representation format, which is called the "Requirements Shell". This format is further explained in subsection 2.3.1.1.

The Volere approach also defines a process model for the entire requirements process. This process model is further explained in subsection 2.3.1.2.

2.3.1.1 *Requirements Shell*

Figure 3 reproduces the generic Volere "Requirements Shell" from (Robertson and Robertson 2010). While the "Requirements Shell" mimics an index card, it is meant as the definition of a representational format that should be used with appropriate technical support for authoring requirements.

The specific technical support adopted in SatisFactory is described in subsection 2.3.3. Because of this support and also because of a number of adaptations of Volere for the purposes of the project, the requirement shell actually used in SatisFactory slightly differs from the generic one.

For instance, SatisFactory uses the simpler MoSCoW (Wikipedia 2015) scheme for requirements prioritization instead of the customer satisfaction and dissatisfaction ratings that are often confusing.

Arguably the two most important fields of the Requirements Shell are "Rationale" and "Fit Criterion". In conjunction with the short "Description" field, they support requirements authors in separating different concerns.

The "Description" is reserved for stating the requirement as factually and concisely as possible. The "Rationale" requires the author to provide an argument for the requirement which may then be contested in the requirements process. The "Fit Criterion" finally requires the author to provide a test for deciding whether a given design actually meets the present requirement. The test needs to be specified in such a way that it is clear how the test can be carried out.

Figure 3: The Volere "Requirements Shell" for representing so-called atomic requirements.

2.3.1.2 Volere Process Model

The Volere process model comprehensively describes the various stages, actors and artefacts that comprise the dynamic execution of the Volere approach. The overview of this process model is shown in "2.3.1.2 - Volere Process Model".

Each of the numbered process steps can be expanded further, illustrating that the overall Volere process model is rather comprehensive and can become relatively complex to carry out.

Depending on the size of the project, the different steps can be carried out with greater or smaller detail and number of iterations, allowing the process to be scaled to the respective needs and available resources. Four steps merit further discussion.

First, "Prototype the Requirements" addresses the important aspect that it is often very difficult to define a fixed set of requirements for implementation. Especially for innovative products this is because

- requirements are often difficult to describe precisely
- requirements are often difficult to assess with respect to their relative merit
- requirements that conflict are often difficult to balance

To address these challenges, SatisFactory makes systematic use of the prototyping techniques during the course of the project work. See also (Gomaa and Scott 1981) for the role of prototyping in requirements engineering.

Second, “Taking Stock of the Specification” addresses the equally important aspect that requirements do not exist alone but always have to be understood in the context of the other requirements that have been defined for the given design. That is to say that the requirements process does not end with authoring individual requirements. In fact, in-depth analysis of the growing set of requirements throughout the requirements process and continued refinement of the requirements (Sutcliffe et al 2003) is paramount to achieving a high-quality specification.

Figure 4: Overview of the Volere Process Model

Third, the “Quality Gateway” addresses the likewise important aspect that requirements can have largely varying quality. This includes both the completeness of the requirement shell as described in subsection 2.3.1.1 as well as the quality of each individual field. The Volere approach recommends an explicit “Quality Gateway” that each requirement has to pass before it can become part of the specification.

Moreover, we employ a specific scheme for formulating user needs (as part of "Stakeholder Wants and Needs"). It is presented in Figure 4. Strict following this syntax supports a correct formulation of the user need according to the definition below.

Definition:

User need – A necessary pre-condition allowing to efficiently fulfill the purpose contained in an actual situation of the context of use.

Furthermore, the syntax helps including two important characteristics in the formulation:

- User needs always refer to and justify what happens in the context of use.
- User needs always consist of a pre-condition (state) and a purpose this pre-condition serves.

Another important aspect to bear in mind when formulating user needs is that they intrinsically affiliate with the problem space. Thus, wording that belongs to the solution space or is related to a concrete technology like "system", "document", "pencil", "keyboard", "press button", "editor", "barcode scanner" etc. should be strongly avoided.

Figure 5: Syntax for formulating user needs

2.3.1.3 Reference for Volere Requirement Types

According to the Volere methodology all information that is part of the requirements specification is viewed as belonging to a particular type. This classification should ease the use of the existing requirements and the coordination between the different experts working on the same project. Altogether there are 33 requirement types that are a subset of the close to 100 subsections of the 27 sections of the Volere requirements specification. In the following Volere requirement types are listed and briefly explained.

Overview

Project Drivers

1. The Purpose of the Project
2. The Stakeholders

Project Constraints

3. Mandated Constraints
4. Naming Conventions and Terminology
5. Relevant Facts and Assumptions

Functional Requirements

6. The Scope of the Work

7. Business Data Model & Data Dictionary
8. The Scope of the Product
9. Functional Requirements

Non-functional Requirements

10. Look and Feel Requirements
11. Usability and Humanity Requirements
12. Performance Requirements
13. Operational and Environmental Requirements
14. Maintainability and Support Requirements
15. Security Requirements
16. Cultural and Political Requirements
17. Legal Requirements

Project Issues

18. Open Issues
19. Off-the-Shelf Solutions
20. New Problems
21. Tasks
22. Migration to the New Product
23. Risks
24. Costs
25. User Documentation and Training
26. Waiting Room
27. Ideas for Solutions

Solution Constraints (3a)

Content *This specifies constraints on the way that the problem must be solved. Describe the mandated technology or solution. Include any appropriate version numbers. You should also explain the reason for using the technology.*

Motivation *To identify constraints that guide the final product. Your client, customer, or user may have design preferences, or only certain solutions may be acceptable. If these constraints are not met, your solution is not acceptable.*

Functional Requirements (9a)

Content *This is a specification for each atomic functional requirement. As for all types of atomic requirements (functional, non-functional, constraint), use the requirements shell as a guide for which attributes should be specified. A full explanation of the atomic requirement and its attributes is included in this template's introductory material.*

Motivation *To specify the detailed functional requirements to be carried out by the product.*

Appearance Requirements (10a)

Content *The section contains requirements relating to the spirit of the product. Your client may have made particular demands for the product, such as corporate branding, colours to be used, and so on. This section captures the requirements for the appearance. Do not attempt to design it until the appearance requirements are known.*

Motivation *To ensure that the appearance of the product conforms to the organization's expectations.*

Style Requirements (10b)

Content *Requirements that specify the mood, style, or feeling of the product, which influences the way a potential customer will see the product. Also, the stakeholders' intentions for the amount of interaction the user is to have with the product.*

In this section, you would also describe the appearance of the package if this is to be a manufactured product. The package may have some requirements as to its size, style, and consistency with other packages put out by your organization. Keep in mind the European laws on packaging, which require that the package not be significantly larger than the product it encloses.

The style requirements that you record here will guide the designers to create a product as envisioned by your client.

Motivation *Given the state of today's market and people's expectations, we cannot afford to build products that have the wrong style. Once the functional requirements are satisfied, it is often the appearance and style of products that determine whether they are successful. Your task in this section is to determine precisely how the product shall appear to its intended consumer.*

Ease of Use Requirements (11a)

Content *This section describes your client's aspirations for how easy it is for the intended users of the product to operate it. The product's usability is derived from the abilities of the expected users of the product and the complexity of its functionality.*

The usability requirements should cover properties such as these:

- *Efficiency of use: How quickly or accurately the user can use the product.*
- *Ease of remembering: How much the casual user is expected to remember about using the product.*
- *Error rates: For some products it is crucial that the user commits very few, or no, errors.*
- *Overall satisfaction in using the product: This is especially important for commercial, interactive products that face a lot of competition. Web sites are a good example.*
- *Feedback: How much feedback the user needs to feel confident that the product is actually accurately doing what the user expects. The necessary degree of feedback will be higher for some products (e.g., safety-critical products) than for others.*

Motivation *To guide the product's designers toward building a product that meets the expectations of its eventual users.*

Personalization and Internationalization Requirements (11b)

Content *This section describes the way in which the product can be altered or configured to take into account the user's personal preferences or choice of language.*

The personalization requirements should cover issues such as the following:

- *Languages, spelling preferences, and language idioms*
- *Currencies, including the symbols and decimal conventions*
- *Personal configuration options*

Motivation *To ensure that the product's users do not have to struggle with, or meekly accept, the builder's cultural conventions.*

Learning Requirements (11c)

Content *Requirements specifying how easy it should be to learn to use the product. This learning curve ranges from zero time for products intended for placement in the public domain (e.g., a parking meter or a web site) to a considerable amount of time for complex, highly technical products. (We know of one product where it was necessary for graduate engineers to spend 18 months in a training program before being qualified to use the product.)*

Motivation *To quantify the amount of time that your client feels is allowable before a user can successfully use the product. This requirement guides designers to understand how users will learn the product. For example, designers may build elaborate interactive help facilities into the product, or the product may be packaged with a tutorial. Alternatively, the product may have to be constructed so that all of its functionality is apparent upon first encountering it.*

Understandability and Politeness Requirements (11d)

Content *This specifies the requirement for the product to be understood by its users. While "usability" refers to ease of use, efficiency, and similar characteristics, "understandability" determines whether the users instinctively know what the product will do for them and how it fits into their view of the world. You can think of understandability as the product being polite to its users and not expecting them to know or learn things that have nothing to do with their business problem. Another aspect of politeness is that the product should not expect the user to input any information to which the product already has access.*

Motivation *To avoid forcing users to learn terms and concepts that are part of the product's internal construction and are not relevant to the users' world. To make the product more comprehensible and thus more likely to be adopted by its intended users.*

Accessibility Requirements (11e)

Content *The requirements for how easy it should be for people with common disabilities to access the product. These disabilities might be related to physical disability or visual, hearing, cognitive, or other abilities.*

Motivation *In many countries it is required that some products be made available to people facing certain types of disabilities. In any event, it is self-defeating to exclude this sizable community of potential customers.*

Speed and Latency Requirements (12a)

Content *Specifies the amount of time available to complete specified tasks. These requirements often refer to response times. They can also refer to the product's ability to operate at a speed suitable for the intended environment.*

Motivation *Some products—usually real-time products—must be able to perform some of their functionality within a given time slot. Failure to do so may mean catastrophic failure (e.g., a ground-sensing radar in an airplane fails to detect an upcoming mountain) or the product will not cope with the required volume of use (e.g., an automated ticket-selling machine).*

Safety-Critical Requirements (12b)

Content *Quantification of the perceived risk of damage to people, property, and environment. Different countries have different standards, so the fit criteria must specify precisely which standards the product must meet.*

Motivation *To understand and highlight the damage that could potentially occur when using the product within the expected operational environment.*

Precision or Accuracy Requirements (12c)

Content *Quantification of the desired accuracy of the results produced by the product.*

Motivation *To set the client's and users' expectations for the precision of the product.*

Reliability and Availability Requirements (12d)

Content *This section quantifies the necessary reliability of the product. The reliability is usually expressed as the allowable time between failures, or the total allowable failure rate. This section also quantifies the expected availability of the product.*

Motivation *It is critical for some products not to fail too often. This section allows you to explore the possibility of failure and to specify realistic levels of service. It also gives you the opportunity to set the client's and users' expectations about the amount of time that the product will be available for use.*

Robustness or Fault-Tolerance Requirements (12e)

Content *Robustness specifies the ability of the product to continue to function under abnormal circumstances.*

Motivation *To ensure that the product is able to provide some or all of its services after or during some abnormal happening in its environment.*

Capacity Requirements (12f)

Content *This section specifies the volumes that the product must be able to deal with and the amount of data stored by the product.*

Motivation *To ensure that the product is capable of processing the expected volumes.*

Scalability or Extensibility Requirements (12g)

Content *This specifies the expected increases in size that the product must be able to handle. As a business grows (or is expected to grow), our software products must increase their capacities to cope with the new volumes.*

Motivation *To ensure that the designers allow capacity for future growth.*

Longevity Requirements (12h)

Content *This specifies the expected lifetime of the product.*

Motivation *To ensure that the product is built based on an understanding of expected return on investment.*

Expected Physical Environment (13a)

Content *This section specifies the physical environment in which the product will operate.*

Motivation *To highlight conditions that might need special requirements, preparations, or training. These requirements ensure that the product is fit to be used in its intended environment.*

Requirements for Interfacing with Adjacent Systems (13b)

Content *This section describes the requirements to interface with partner applications and/or devices that the product needs to successfully operate.*

Motivation *Requirements for the interfaces to other applications often remain undiscovered until implementation time. Avoid a high degree of rework by discovering these requirements early.*

Productization Requirements (13c)

Content *Any requirements that are necessary to make the product into a distributable or saleable item. It is also appropriate to describe here the operations needed to install a software product successfully.*

Motivation *To ensure that if work must be done to get the product out the door, then that work becomes part of the requirements. Also, to quantify the client's and users' expectations about the amount of time, money, and resources they will need to allocate to install the product.*

Release Requirements (13d)

Content *Specification of the intended release cycle for the product and the form that the release shall take.*

Motivation *To make everyone aware of how often you intend to produce new releases of the product.*

Maintenance Requirements (14a)

Content *A quantification of the time necessary to make specified changes to the product.*

Motivation *To make everyone aware of the maintenance needs of the product.*

Supportability Requirements (14b)

Content *This specifies the level of support that the product requires. Support is often provided via a help desk. If people will provide support for the product, that service is considered part of the product: Are there any requirements for that support? You might also build support into the product itself, in which case this section is the place to write those requirements.*

Motivation *To ensure that the support aspect of the product is adequately specified.*

Adaptability Requirements (14c)

Content *Description of other platforms or environments to which the product must be ported.*

Motivation *To publicise the client's and users' expectations about the platforms on which the product will be able to run.*

Access Requirements (15a)

Content *Specification of who is authorized to access to the product (both functionality and data), under what circumstances that access is granted, and to which parts of the product access is allowed.*

Motivation *To understand the expectations for confidentiality aspects of the system.*

Integrity Requirements (15b)

Content *Specification of the required integrity of databases and other files, and of the product itself.*

Motivation *To understand the expectations for the integrity of the product's data. To specify what the product will do to ensure its integrity in the case of an unwanted happening such as attack from the outside or unintentional misuse by an authorized user.*

Privacy Requirements (15c)

Content *Specification of what the product has to do to ensure the privacy of individuals about whom it stores information. The product must also ensure that all laws related to privacy of an individual's data are observed.*

Motivation *To ensure that the product complies with the law, and to protect the individual privacy of your customers. Few people today look kindly on organizations that do not observe their privacy.*

Audit Requirements (15d)

Content *Specification of what the product has to do (usually retain records) to permit the required audit checks.*

Motivation *To build a system that complies with the appropriate audit rules.*

Immunity Requirements (15e)

Content *The requirements for what the product has to do to protect itself from infection by unauthorized or undesirable software programs, such as viruses, worms, malware, spyware and any other undesirable interference.*

Motivation *To build a product that is as secure as possible from malicious interference.*

Cultural Requirements (16a)

Content *This section contains requirements that are specific to the sociological factors that affect the acceptability of the product. If you are developing a product for foreign markets, then these requirements are particularly relevant.*

Motivation *To bring out in the open requirements that are difficult to discover because they are outside the cultural experience of the developers.*

Political Requirements (16b)

Content *This section contains requirements that are specific to the political factors that affect the acceptability of the product.*

Motivation *To understand requirements that sometimes appear irrational.*

Compliance Requirements (17a)

Content *A statement specifying the legal requirements for this system.*

Motivation *To comply with the law so as to avoid later delays, lawsuits, and legal fees.*

Standards Requirements (17b)

Content *A statement specifying applicable standards and referencing detailed standards descriptions. This does not refer to the law of the land—think of it as an internal law imposed by your company.*

Motivation *To comply with standards so as to avoid later delays.*

2.3.2 Requirements in the SatisFactory design process

As illustrated in Figure 6 SatisFactory has adopted an iterative human-centred design approach. Different types of artefacts are used for describing information relevant for the individual stages of the process. For example, user needs and scenarios are used to capture results of the analysis of the context of use, cf. SatisFactory D1.2. And they are used as background for co-creating and illustrating use cases and requirements as well as features for the systems to be developed. (Holbrook 1990, Chin et al. 1997, Glinz 2000, Sutcliffe 2003)

By using the online support presented in section 2.3.3, the authoring of user needs and requirements, with the possibility of authoring of features and other development issues, allows for creating a network of interrelated design artefacts in the interest of achieving design traceability as advocated by ISO 9241, see also (Ramesch and Jarke 2001). The following picture present the Iterative human-centred design approach adopted in SatisFactory following ISO 9241, part 210 (ISO 2010) and the allocation of the appropriate work packages.

Figure 6: Iterative human-centred design approach

In order to ease the formulation of requirements we employ a pre-step to Volere requirements where the so-called *requirements for use* (also known as *user requirements* or *usage requirements*) are formulated. Requirements for use are requirements that are directly following from the context of use. In fact, they are derived from the user needs.

Definition

Requirement for use – A necessary activity a user conducts with the system– describing the activity and not the technical realisation.

Requirements for use have the following characteristics:

- Requirements for use based on user needs in the context of use
- Requirements for use are interpretations of a user need (technology independent)

To support their formulation the scheme presented in Figure 7 should be used.

Figure 7: Syntax for formulating requirements for use

2.3.3 Online support for requirements in SatisFactory

For the creation and management of information elements of a design process, a number of different approaches have been suggested (Stufflebeam et al. 2003, Penna et al. 2003). In the authors experience most tools that go beyond Microsoft Word and Excel have little prospect of being used on a broad basis among a heterogeneous group of partners in international R&D projects. And while MS Word and Excel are certainly adequate for representing a set of user needs or requirements, they have not proven effective in sustainably supporting a continuous and iterative design process.

In the interest of providing other means to reach this objective, Fraunhofer FIT has developed an approach for using the general-purpose web-based ticketing system JIRA³ for distributed and collaborative authoring and management of design related information (Easterbrook 1993, Jarke and Pohl 1994).

JIRA uses the issue paradigm which is generally known from bug-tracking and customer-support systems. This paradigm provides a flexible and most importantly light-weight way of creating and managing information items, assigning responsibilities and supporting adapted levels of control for the design process by way of role-based workflows.

The SatisFactory JIRA project space can be found at the following address and is hosted, maintained and supported by Fraunhofer FIT: <https://jira.fit.fraunhofer.de/jira/browse/SAFA/>.

Two general issue types are currently available in the JIRA space of the SatisFactory project.

The first is the "User Need" that supports the activities of the analysis of the context of use that result in the identification of the user needs based on the data gathered during the ethnographic research that is conducted at the pilot sites COMAU, SUNLIGHT and CERTH. The creation dialog for user needs in JIRA is shown in Figure 8.

The second is the "Volere Requirement" that is formed according to the Volere requirements template, also called "Requirements Shell", that is depicted in Figure 3. As already mentioned in subsection 2.3.1.1 the generic Volere requirements template has been slightly adapted to ease the

³ <https://de.atlassian.com/software/jira>

prioritization of the requirements and enhance the process of authoring and collaboration. In particular, customer satisfaction and dissatisfaction ratings have been replaced by a more “natural” scheme, the MoSCoW method, and the fields have been classified in “Mandatory” and “Supporting entries” in order to increase usability for the authoring task. Figure 9 and Figure 10 show the two groups of entry fields in the requirements creation dialog. This classification, however, does not mean that “Supporting entries” are not important and thus should not be filled in! In fact, the opposite is the case: The supporting entries “Requirement Type”, “Dependencies” and “Conflicts” are crucial to support of searching, reviewing, planning implementation and generally making sense of the requirements. Thus, they are indispensable for passing the quality control of a requirement.

Project*

Issue Type* ?

Some issue types are unavailable due to incompatible field configuration and/or workflow associations.

Summary*

Description

Attachment No file selected.

The maximum file upload size is 10.00 MB.

Create another

Figure 8: Screenshot of the user need creation dialog in SatisFactory

Project*

Issue Type* ?

Some issue types are unavailable due to incompatible field configuration and/or workflow associations.

Mandatory Supporting entries

Summary*

Priority ?

Description

Why is the requirement considered important or necessary?

Fit Criterion

A quantification of the requirement used to determine whether the requirement is met

Source

From which stakeholder and which event did this requirement emerge?

Attachment No files selected.

The maximum file upload size is 10.00 MB.

Create another

Figure 9: "Mandatory" part of the Volere Requirement creation dialog

Project*

Issue Type* ?

Some issue types are unavailable due to incompatible field configuration and/or workflow associations.

Mandatory Supporting entries

Requirement Type

Dependencies

Other requirements with a change effect

Conflicts

Requirements that contradict this one

Create another

Figure 10: "Supporting entries" part of the Volere Requirement creation dialog

In the “Annex 2 – Requirements template (Volere)” the template adopted for the Satisfactory project is attached.

A state diagram defining possible states of an issue and appropriate transitions between states has been implemented for both types of issues, “User Need” and “Volere Requirement”, in the SatisFactory requirements engineering process. The state diagrams are shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12.

In particular Figure 11 shows that as soon as a user need has been created it is in an “open” state. After an “open” user need has passed the quality check should be set to “quality check passed” state. The state “duplicate” can be assigned from all states (here the two mentioned above) and means that this user need actually is redundant to another user need, i.e. it duplicates another existing issue. Logic depicted in Figure 12 is the same as for the previous description.

Figure 11: State diagram of issue type “User Need”

Figure 12: State diagram of issue type “Volere Requirement”

2.4 PROGRESS BEYOND FIRST DOCUMENT ITERATION

2.4.1 Approach

To further deepen the understanding of the context in factories and to guide the further design of the SatisFactory concepts and platform, FIT undertook a series of observations, user-testing, and interviews with users at SUNLIGHT and COMAU. The tests and interviews took place in November 2015 at Sunlight and in January 2016 at COMAU. The fit of the concepts to the environment was evaluated and the necessary changes are presented in Section 2.4.3 (“Lessons learned”).

2.4.2 Methodology

The methods used included:

- Observation, explained in Section 2.2.3.3. Observations were carried out first in April at SUNLIGHT and CPERI, then in November again at SUNLIGHT.
- Contextual Enquiry at SUNLIGHT both in April and November 2015. The method is explained below in section 2.4.2.1.
- Semi-structured interviews at the same times as the observations. The method was explained in section 2.2.3.1.
- User testing with thinking aloud, explained below in section 2.4.2.2. Tests were carried out with a paper prototype at SUNLIGHT in November 2015, and with a medium-fidelity prototype at COMAU in January 2016

2.4.2.1 Contextual Inquiry

Contextual inquiries are specific interviews where users are interviewed in their workplace, while they are working. It is important that the interviewers do not negatively interfere or disturb the user. A kind of master-apprentice relationship develops, where the user has to teach the designer how the work is done. The designer asks questions, trying to learn as much as possible about the process. At the end, he or she makes a summary of what was learned, and the user has to correct or give feedback on this summary.

2.4.2.2 User-testing with thinking aloud

User testing with thinking aloud is a method wherein a user is asked to complete certain tasks using a prototype of the system. The user has to think aloud while using the system, and openly say whatever comes to his or her mind. This allows the designers to understand the user’s mental image (understanding) of the system, and to note where this understanding is different from what the designers intend. The problems thus found are analysed and the design is changed to either match the user’s understanding, or to better communicate to the user the intents and actions available through the system’s interface.

2.4.3 Lessons learned

The detailed findings from the research done in this period are presented below. The number of findings in each category confirms that:

- the general direction and understanding of the context is sound
- the context was understood correctly
- the tasks that the system should fulfil were understood
- the prototype UI can be considerably improved.

This is a very good result considering the development phase of the system. UI problems were expected, while no unexpected or conflicting results were found with respect to approach, context, and tasks.

2.4.3.1 General Approach

- Being rewarded (with cash or other valuable items) for good suggestions seems to be very important for this suggestions approach to work. (as it has been confirmed by further interviews, in particular with a human resources department representative who is responsible for implementing WCM suggestions for improvement strategy).
- We need to clarify whether prioritization of suggestions makes sense, or whether every suggestion should be equally important
- Anonymity of the suggestions is seen as a barrier to rewarding suggesters. For some cases, however, being able to make an anonymous suggestion seems to be a preferable option. The system needs to accommodate both cases

2.4.3.2 Context Description

- It needs to be clarified whether the system should take office workers into account, given they are not “factory workers” in the strict sense of the word.
- Access to the system should be provided also from the offices for office workers to be able to add suggestions too.

2.4.3.3 Task description and user needs

- The user needs to know how long the suggestion has been already there, in order to evaluate possible next steps.
- Durations of different status phases of a suggestion (like how long it was opened, how long in implementation, when it was closed) should be visible.
- There should be some kind of expiration date for suggestions. 3 months seems like a good starting point to test further

- First feedback on submitted suggestions should be provided soon after the suggestion. Suggested value: one week.
- Investigate whether a vote for or against a suggestion when commenting should be introduced, like a thumb up or thumb down
- We should clarify which date should be shown for a suggestion: date of last activity or submission date.
- A point scale for the evaluation of a contribution could be used, in order to assess the relative importance and the contribution towards a prize.
- The contact data of the person responsible for a decision on the suggestion need to be revised. Not all of them are necessary.
- A possibility for adding videos and other files is needed
- A confirmation for suggestion being read by the decision makers is necessary
- Decision makers should be reminded periodically to about suggestions they need to decide upon or give feedback to.
- Suggester expects a minimum length of feedback to feel taken seriously. Managers should be encouraged to write at least a minimum amount of words in the feedback.
- The process should be implemented not solely in the system: additional human activities (human communication) should be part of the workflow.

2.4.3.4 *Prototype UI*

- UIs should be in the native language of the employees. This is especially important for prototyping and testing.
- Make the UI language clearer and simpler, e.g. "Send suggestion" or "Save suggestion"
- Clean up the interaction to bring it in line with the user's expectation from other systems
- Clean up the interface and avoid duplicated actions and confusing layouts.
- Make prototype work locally for performance reasons.
- Clearly define the behaviour of the closing icon in the "Add suggestion" screen to be consistent with the OS.
- "Other ideas" seems to be not very clear term for the category meaning that all other suggestions should go there.
- The colour concept should be adapted according to the meanings of the safety-critical environment at the factory, in order not to confuse workers with green, red, or yellow colours that actually don't have the usual meaning to them. For UI elements with specific signalling meanings a "traffic light" (green, yellow, red) concept should be used.
- The relationship between commenting, comments and the status of a suggestion is not clear.
- A better concept for representation of chronological relations between suggestions and actions is needed.
- A way is needed to quickly find a user's own suggestions amid the others'.
- The meaning that these (responsible) people are involved in the decision-making process about the particular suggestion is currently not clear, and should be made clearer in the next version of the prototype.

- Consider whether a login system using the security badge of the user would make the interaction better or easier in any way.
- Visually it is currently not very clear what is the actual suggestion text and what is the modification. Make it clearer in the representation.
- The affordances for accessing contact data of the responsible decision makers should be clearer.
- The category system should be rethought as to usefulness and clarity
- Icons used for product categories should not conflict with icons used in other contexts or systems used by the user.
- It is not clear to the user what the elements on the interface mean or can do. This may be partly due to the language barrier, but this only highlights the lack of multiple-coding in the representation of the actions.
- It should be made clear, through graphical and structural elements, that the suggestions detail page represents a dialog between people and not a library of content.
- Use the same familiar layout where a tradition of such improvement programs exists.
- Clicking on a category should not open the explanation of this category. This was unexpected for users. Listing suggestions of that category, or adding a new one might be better. However this needs to be decided after deciding on whether the category system is useful at all.
- The just-added suggestions should be easily findable in the list of all suggestions.

2.4.4 Jira Platform

Twenty-nine new issues were entered in JIRA as a result of the above research. The issues that passed the quality control are summarized below.

Req#	Issue ID	Requirement/Need
61	SAFA-192	Association of the workers' names with their suggestions
62	SAFA-193	Time duration availability of the suggestions
63	SAFA-197	UIs shall be in the formal language of the deployment country
64	SAFA-198	All UI interaction parts should be clearly visible
65	SAFA-200	The UIs should be user-friendly
66	SAFA-202	Suggestions will be sorted by submission date
67	SAFA-203	Suggestions filtering support
68	SAFA-204	Personal statistics available to the users
69	SAFA-205	Evaluation of a contribution will support point scale
70	SAFA-206	The product shall keep the prize detail separate from the system
71	SAFA-207	Suggestions system should support suggestion categories
72	SAFA-208	Open suggestions shall be sent to the decision makers
73	SAFA-211	The suggestion submission form shall be in similar format as the pre-existing manual system
74	SAFA-215	Gamification must be presented in several subcomponents of satisfactory

SATISFACTORY

75	SAFA-217	The gamification framework must support PBL
76	SAFA-218	No participant of the gamification shall be exposed as looser
77	SAFA-220	Other SatisFactory components shall submit points of participants to the gamification framework
78	SAFA-221	The gamification framework should allow workers to participate individually as well as in teams
79	SAFA-222	All urgent tasks shall be properly allocated to the employees
80	SAFA-223	Current location of employee shall be taken into account by the RA & HR workload balancing tool
81	SAFA-224	The system should be able to interface existing measurement tools and infrastructure
82	SAFA-225	All historical data from the shop-floor shall be available through CIDEM
83	SAFA-226	All information exchanged and stored within SatisFactory components shall be in a common format understandable from all components
84	SAFA-227	Timely workers notification in case of an alarm
85	SAFA-228	The UI shall provide maps visualization for a more concrete understanding
86	SAFA-229	The messages provided by the system shall be clear and easy to understand
87	SAFA-230	The SatisFactory components shall be able to store and retrieve large amounts of data
88	SAFA-231	In case one or more components are not reachable on the network, the system shall be able to manage the whole operation without them and their data
89	SAFA-232	Communication among SatisFactory components will be platform independent

3. CONTEXT OF USE ANALYSIS

In this chapter the production processes, as well as the actors and stakeholders considered in the SatisFactory project are analysed. First section gives the main definitions, while the second one introduces details of the considered manufacturing processes with the associated workers involved for each domain.

3.1 PRODUCTION PROCESSES, ACTORS AND STAKEHOLDERS

3.1.1 Production processes

SatisFactory project started the user needs analysis, focusing on the areas of expertise of the end-user partners composing the consortium. Such processes cover a wide range of European industrial sectors. They refer in particular to the discrete manufacturing, represented by the application in Automotive & Machining, where COMAU provides his expertise, by the Batteries Manufacturing, led by SunLight and, finally, the Chemical Process Industry, coordinated by CERTH.

Main goal of the SatisFactory Project is the improvement of the Process Operator Workplace, however to deeply analyse such enhancement it is compulsory to take into consideration also the coordinating functions as well as the design and engineering roles. The three main layers afore mentioned are depicted in the following pyramid.

Figure 13: End-users test-beds reference model

3.1.2 Actors and Stakeholders

In the Satisfactory Project, the term “Actors” identify all specific roles involved in the manufacturing process, while all supporting design and engineering roles, as well as connected staff functions are named “Stakeholders”. More precisely the Project will focus and develop applications for the “Actors” such as Process Operators, and their first management level (i.e. Team Leaders, Foremen

and Coordinators). Additional figures that will be considered in SatisFactory, are the roles devoted to design and engineering activities of the workplaces, as well as ergonomics validations.

Figure 14: Categorization of Actors and Stakeholders

The previously described model can be extended, considering more roles in the companies, and their supply chains, e.g. tier 1 suppliers. These figures have been included in the following representation, and they will be part of the next iterations of the requirements engineering process.

Figure 15: Categorization of Internal Stakeholders and Connected Stakeholders

A preliminary analysis of the legislation, related to safety and ergonomics in the workplace has been performed by the end-users and technological partners. The result is attached in "Annex 3 – Legislation review" and "Annex 4 – Workplaces ergonomics".

3.2 DESCRIPTION OF THE CONTEXT OF USE

Hereafter the processes and related actors & stakeholders for each of the three end-user scenarios are described. Moreover some highlights of the maintenance actors are presented.

3.2.1 COMAU – Automotive discrete manufacturing

3.2.1.1 Process

COMAU has taken into consideration 3 specific manufacturing processes that have key roles in its core business. In particular the first one is developed within the Robotics Business Unit and is focused on the robot hollow wrist assembly. The second and the third processes consider two applications of the Body Welding business unit, more precisely the welding guns assembly process and the welding lines assembly are analysed.

- **Robotics - Hollow wrist assembly**

Used in welding applications, hollow wrist robots or robots with cabling integrated through the arm, have become a staple in automated welding systems. Designed with the cables integrated in the arm of the robot, they are easy to install into a new or existing cell, increase productivity and product quality, and reduce wear and tear on expensive cables.

Main advantages are respectively Easy to program/simulate, Larger work envelope, Higher robot density, Greater accessibility and Simplified tooling.

COMAU produces different models of robots with hollow wrist with different sizes and payloads according to the customers' needs (patented solution EP1970171A1).

In the pictures below is represented a Smart5 NJ4-90, an hollow wrist robot with a payload of 90 kg, used mainly for welding applications in the automotive industry and a schema of the hollow wrist.

Figure 16: COMAU Smart5 NJ4-90 hollow wrist robot

Figure 17: COMAU robot hollow wrist

The mechanical assembly of these robots is done internally in COMAU completely by operators and it is composed by a specific sequence of operations that must be followed accurately in order to guarantee the performances and high level of reliability that characterized COMAU products.

In particular the assembly process includes operations such as cleaning of the mechanical parts coming from foundry/machining, gears and spacers assembly, sealing and grease filling, test of tolerances & mechanical couplings and finally marking electrical motors & wiring assembly.

- **Body Welding – Welding guns assembly**

Resistive spot welding is a process in which contacting metal surfaces are joined by the heat obtained from resistance to electric current. Work-pieces are held together under pressure exerted by electrodes. The process uses two shaped copper alloy electrodes to concentrate welding current into a small "spot" and to simultaneously clamp the sheets together. Forcing a large current through the spot will melt the metal and form the weld. The attractive feature of spot welding is that a lot of energy can be delivered to the spot in a very short time.

COMAU developed a Spot Welding Guns family, specifically developed for the automotive sector. These products are characterized by simplicity and modularity. Three standard chassis provide a robust and compact solution; 100% of typical car body shop requirements are satisfied with this versatile product. Main features are:

- Robust and compact
- COMAU Servo actuator
- COMAU transformer (MFDC)
- Equalisation through robot compensation
- No external cables
- RobCAD Simulation effectively 100%
- Fireproof (ABS VH-0800E) cover protects from spatter / contamination

Following a picture of a typical welding gun integrated with a robot system and a mechanical drawing of a welding gun are provided.

Figure 18: COMAU Smart5 NJ4-90 with COMAU Compact welding gun

Figure 19: COMAU Compact welding gun

COMAU welding gun assembly process involves the preparation of the mechanical structure of the body with the transformer, followed by the integration of the arms with the copper tips holders and the linear motor. Finally the wiring and piping complete the installation.

The mechanical assembly is followed by a testing and certification that include a fine tuning of the welding parameters.

- **Body Welding - Welding lines assembly**

One of the main stages of the car production is the assembly and welding of the car body. This process is performed on robotized production lines, where automated clamps and fixtures hold the metal parts in position while robots perform welding operations.

COMAU is a global leader in advanced production systems for vehicle full body, components manufacturing, as well as turnkey body shops.

One of the main components of these manufacturing lines are the reference tools including clamps and fixtures, needed to give the elements the proper geometry and characteristics of the subsystems of the whole car body that has to be manufactured.

Following a picture of a body welding line is provided, as well as an example of a reference gate that holds a body-side in position during welding operations.

Figure 20: COMAU body-welding line

Figure 21: COMAU body-side fixtures

One of the main phases of COMAU body-welding lines assembly process is the construction of the reference structures that hold the sheet-metal parts. These operations are performed by the installation of clamps and fixtures on the mechanical frame, followed by fluidics piping to connect compressed air and electrical wiring of the mechatronics devices. These operations are done following detailed mechanical and electrical drawings provided by the engineering department. The mechanical and electrical assembly is followed by a testing and certification that include a fine tuning of the clamping system and I/O testing.

3.2.1.2 **Actors & Stakeholders**

In COMAU use-cases three different groups of resources have been considered. Starting from the design & engineering to the process execution is it possible to identify the Design & Ergonomics Engineer, the Process Operator, and his responsible, the Technical Leader.

- **Process Operator**

The Process Operator is a mechatronics worker, responsible for the construction of machinery and production systems, from the assembly of single components to the full integrated system, including the following tasks:

- mechanical assembly
- electrical wiring
- fluidics piping
- preliminary and final testing
- troubleshooting
- support to power-up and final delivery to customer (commissioning)

These operations are performed in a team and under the supervision of the Technical Leader.

Figure 22: Process Operators during piping installation on a robot arm

- **Technical Leader**

The Technical Leader is responsible for coordinating the resources (i.e. Process Operators) needed to carry out a specific project, under constraints of customer's specifications, internal resources availability, project timeline, budget. He must guarantee the requested technical performances from the early stages of preliminary design, to the detailed design of machines and manufacturing systems, until the final customer's acceptance, with the support of Project Manager. He has the responsibility for:

- technical design of machines and lines with dedicated team
- design team coordination
- external suppliers management
- ensuring the project progress according to milestones
- interfacing with workers employed in actual building of machinery in the shop floor.

- **Design & Ergonomics Engineer**

The Design & Ergonomics Engineer is responsible for detailed design of the technical solutions needed to complete a specific customer's project, under the coordination of the Technical Leader. He must guarantee, within his area of expertise, the full compliance of the project with the expected requirements, managing all aspects related to:

- layout of machines
- mechanical design
- electrical/software/hydraulic design
- ergonomics and safety issues
- preparation of drawings and diagrams for machinery and accessory parts construction.

3.2.1.3 *Progress beyond first iteration in COMAU use-cases*

Since the first submission of deliverable D1.1, several activities have been carried out in order to give a priority level to the different use-cases proposed in the document and focus the developments in a particular application. In particular the "Hollow-Wrist" assembly, due to the patents pending on its internal design, has been replaced with the traditional wrist assembly of the NJ110/130 Robots family. This assembly work-station contains a subset of tools and working areas of the previous one and unlike all the others where there are several different components assembled with a variable mix, it is a mono-product area. This allows to simplify the procedures creation and implementation in the SatisFactory platform. Following picture shows the NJ110/130 robot wrist.

Once identified component and the operations conducted in the related work-place, the activities focused on the requirements analysis for the needed hardware: actual instruments are completely manual / mechanical. This activity has been conducted analysing the actual operation / assembly procedures and actual tools and measurement instruments, and it led to the creation / modification of the following requirements:

Req #	Key	Summary
1	SAFA-4	The HMIs of the platform shall be attractive and easy to use
2	SAFA-13	The tools and applications must be 24/7 operational
3	SAFA-17	The tools shall be able to successfully exchange data with the existing infrastructure at the shop floors
6	SAFA-24	SatisFactory components must have a successful and continuous data exchange with CIDEM
8	SAFA-31	Successful integration of all heterogeneous devices of the shop floors
11	SAFA-34	The system shall be able to monitoring actors through privacy preserving sensors
12	SAFA-37	The platform should present training procedures through multimedia content
14	SAFA-41	All shop floor data must be stored in a common database
16	SAFA-58	The AR components of SatisFactory must have continuous access to the database
17	SAFA-59	The platform shall support social communication between actors
18	SAFA-62	Gamification tools will be interactive with the actors

SATISFACTORY

19	SAFA-65	AR tools will have the ability to interpret the displaying operating procedures
20	SAFA-66	Multi-Layered Description of Operating Procedures (OP-MLD) Realtime Ready
21	SAFA-67	The platform will allow uncoupling of Multi-Layered Description of operating procedures and their Interactive Real-time Visualization
22	SAFA-69	The symbols/terminology of the data presented on the glasses must be effective and easy to understand
23	SAFA-73	Continuous and successful data transfer between glasses and the database of each shop floor
24	SAFA-75	The frame of the glasses shall be optimal for the workers
27	SAFA-93	Alarms shall be accompanied with a description
28	SAFA-101	Different opinions shall be exchanged during the operation of a task
39	SAFA-105	The system shall provide means of submitting suggestions for improvements available, in order to contribute to modernization and overall improvement of working conditions
34	SAFA-120	The communication product shall be open for non-work-related content
35	SAFA-131	Competition shall be informal and friendly
36	SAFA-132	The product shall not restrict workers' autonomy
39	SAFA-135	The system shall not influence workers' carefulness
40	SAFA-136	The system shall be applicable when workers wear a mask
42	SAFA-140	Support mobile users
43	SAFA-143	Support feedback answers on suggestions for improvement
44	SAFA-146	Release answers/feedback on suggestions for improvements to operators
47	SAFA-154	Continuous access to training procedures
49	SAFA-172	The system shall be able to combine the heterogeneous acquired data from the shop floor
57	SAFA-189	HMI tool (on Mobile device) could be used to take photos from the working area
58	SAFA-192	Association of the workers' names with their suggestions
59	SAFA-193	Time duration availability of the suggestions
60	SAFA-197	UIs shall be in the formal language of the deployment country
61	SAFA-198	All UI interaction parts should be clearly visible
62	SAFA-200	The UIs should be user-friendly
63	SAFA-202	Suggestions will be sorted by submission date
64	SAFA-203	Suggestions filtering support
65	SAFA-204	Personal statistics available to the users
66	SAFA-205	Evaluation of a contribution will support point scale
67	SAFA-206	The product shall keep the prize detail separate from the system
68	SAFA-207	Suggestions system should support suggestion categories
69	SAFA-208	Open suggestions shall be sent to the decision makers

70	SAFA-211	The suggestion submission form shall be in similar format as the pre-existing manual system
71	SAFA-215	Gamification must be presented in several subcomponents of satisfactory
72	SAFA-217	The gamification framework must support PBL
73	SAFA-218	No participant of the gamification shall be exposed as loser
74	SAFA-220	Other SatisFactory components shall submit points of participants to the gamification framework
75	SAFA-221	The gamification framework should allow workers to participate individually as well as in teams
76	SAFA-222	All urgent tasks shall be properly allocated to the employees
80	SAFA-226	All information exchanged and stored within SatisFactory components shall be in a common format understandable from all components
81	SAFA-227	Timely workers notification in case of an alarm
82	SAFA-228	The UI shall provide maps visualization for a more concrete understanding
83	SAFA-229	The messages provided by the system shall be clear and easy to understand
86	SAFA-232	Communication among SatisFactory components will be platform independent

One important aspect of the manual operations conducted in robot wrists assembly is that both hands are required to perform the operations, thus different presentation tools from tables are required, such as fixed terminals, docking stations or glasses. This aspect led to the modification of following requirements:

Req. #	Key	Summary
36	SAFA-132	The product shall not restrict workers' autonomy
39	SAFA-135	The system shall not influence workers' carefulness
40	SAFA-136	The system shall be applicable when workers wear a mask

Following months will foresee an important phase that includes the most consistent implementation activities in this use-case, this will lead to concrete results that will be iteratively tested with shop-floor operators and improved thanks to their feedbacks and suggestions.

3.2.1.4 *Further Progresses Achieved with Third and Last Iteration onto COMAU Use-Cases*

Third and last iteration lead over COMAU Use-Cases implied some major refinements. In general COMAU ShopFloor landscape changed a bit, since grey robots started to be produced, instead of

traditional red robot depicted in several images above (e.g. Figure 16, Figure 18, ...). This did not changed directly the prescribed Use-Cases, but contributed a lot to the improvement of the general sense of cooperation and friendliness on WorkPlaces, both on COMUA site and onto customer premises; while red was addressing people attention signalling them warning, grey represents the idea of a user-friendly automation, promoting human – machine cooperation.

Here below pictures of new, grey versions of “NJ4 90” robot, the “Hollow-Wrist” model that was – during first iteration – meant to be subject of first scenario (see Figure 23 below) and of “NJ 110 / 130”, whose wrist assembly process started to be taken into account from secondo iteration on (Figure 24).

Figure 23: COMAU NJ4 90 in new, grey outfit

Figure 24: COMAU NJ 110 / 130 in new, grey outfit

Lot of efforts in COMAU have been undertaken to reveal the beauty of automation throughout a transparent showcase.

COMAU believes in intelligence, cooperation and agility at shopfloor Automation level.

This is the vision beyond AURA – Advanced Use Robotic Arm – an innovative solution making real cooperation between COMAU high payload robots (60 and 110 kg, the highest payloads on the market) and man happens. AURA has been already demonstrated in applications to luxury brands Final Assembly processes.

AURA combines, perception and predictive systems: AURA robots are powered by a special covering, equipped with sensitive areas which can simultaneously perceive the proximity and the contact with a person, or any other automation component, allowing for M2M communication and interoperability. Moreover, auto-adaptability of the system is ensured by AURA ability to modify robot trajectory accordingly to a contact. User experience is empowered by an integrated vision system which enables AURA robots to predict the movements of people it is interacting with, into area of action.

Figure 25: COMAU AURA (Advanced Use Robotic Arm)

Another best innovation case is represented by COMAU Amico, a humanoid robot, hinting at cooperation between machines and, increasingly, between man and machine, ensuring precision and effectiveness. Furthermore, Amico wears sensors making its “hand” effectors (grippers) – rather than end effectors – capable of self-adjusting their grasp.

Figure 26: COMAU Amico at EMO MILANO 2015 Fair

Thus, much more attention has been devoted to robot wrist assembly scenario and use case; this lead to the decision of not further inspecting COMAU Welding Guns process, due also to internal process re-layouting and job sharing. To even boost the impact that the chosen scenario would be invested of, it has been decided to reserve an area in COMAU ShowRoom for an ad-hoc fitted

booth, representing the master for a new concept of WorkPlace that would be introduced into COMAU NJ 110 / 130 wrist assembly real workflow and deserves to be spread across the factory and to other potentially interested companies, that can experience it into COMAU ShowRoom.

Finally, the third scenario regarding internal commissioning of welding lines, have been totally distorted. Instead of focusing again on same step of product value-chain, i.e. the “baby” of automation, the idea has been to move forward throughout COMAU product life-cycle, and apply SatisFactory principles over maintenance activities, lead – why not but not limited to – over COMAU automated welding lines, and to be then further extended first to other COMAU Automation Systems Business Unit solutions and then to all other Business Units (like Powertrain Machining).

This implied the flanking of other professional profiles to main involved actors and stakeholders, especially the ones related to following COMAU products / lines when their property passes over to customers. This professional family comprehends all people involved in the so-called Customer Care Departments, structured per COMAU Business Unit. Customer Care adepts range from highly-skilled problem-solving technicians, to managerial engineers, to software engineers, other high-profile technical assistance experts (mechanical engineers, ...) and even logistics-related personnel, dealing with spare parts business.

The initially drafted scenario foresaw one maintenance technician receiving a call for intervention based on a task scheduled on Her / His maintenance calendar, automatically generated accordingly to following drivers:

- Automation data / information automatically received from different layer into automation control systems architecture.
This means they can be limited to just mere alarms or they can even be intelligent outputs triggered by certain machine process parameters, elaborated by analytics systems.
Such messages / dispatches should have been somehow enriched by some additional information regarding physical objects involved, cause-effect diagnostics, determining the intervention to be performed, its type, skills needed, tools required to fix it, ...
- Maintenance technicians availability in terms of effort assessment.
- Maintenance technicians professional profiling based on technical skills against required skills for intervention performance.
- Maintenance technicians position inside the shopfloor (minimum intervention time assessed throughout minimum distance from intervention point calculations achieved through indoor localization systems).

Due to critical reliance of such solution on other systems, in the end the application should be shaped as follows:

- Maintenance technician has to perform a planned maintenance intervention based on Her / His work schedule;
- She / He reaches for intervention target;
- She / He starts a maintenance intervention procedure with multi-format support (markerless Augmented Reality, immersive Virtual Reality, videos, pictures, documentation ranging from PDF manuals to drawings, ...);
- In case of troubles in task execution She / He can ask for a technical support expert starting a call;

- During the call there would be the possibility of sharing pictures bi-directionally, of receiving multi-format documentation on maintenance technician side and, more important, to stream video from ShopFloor to remote support technician;
- On Her / His side technical assistance expert can – in the best case – add information (text or hand-drawn instructions) that will be then real-time displayed on maintenance technician side in Augmented Reality.

No information has been given in the above about digital support used since one of the most compelling challenge would be how to “re-invent” commercial devices, to make them portable, even wearable and to avoid hindering the technician while performing Her / His job. This would mean for example using smart glasses (depending on intervention duration and repeatability / frequency of activity) or even tablets, but imagining on how they can be used in an effective way keeping hands free.

3.2.2 CERTH/CPERI – Chemical continuous process

3.2.2.1 Significant infrastructure/Technical Equipment/Products/Services

CERTH/CPERI has a wide range of industrial automation systems and industrial software platforms. The automated systems are used for process control and remote monitoring (SCADA, DCS, PLC based). Also Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition Systems (SCADA) for chemical and energy production processes are in operation with respective middleware software, with OPC connectivity. CERTH/CPERI has developed and supports a wide multi-sensorial network of heterogeneous distributed systems (indicative industrial protocols: CANBus, Profibus, EtherCat, RS485).

Within the project, CERTH/CPERI will utilize its industrial automation infrastructure for the deployment of the integrated Reference Architecture Platform to CERTH/CPERI’s process plants where the Industrial Lab cases will take place and selected shop-floor processes will be used as a test bed for SatisFactory products and solutions.

CERTH/CPERI’s infrastructure consists of numerous experimental industrial process systems where information is propagated through a network backbone that facilitates data exchange from and to the input/output field of respective units. Each unit has sensors that acquire various signals which are distributed in a wide area and are connected using industrial networks. The monitoring and control is performed in real time and cover actions and events that take place throughout the life cycle of the information, starting from the encoding at the physical layer to the knowledge sharing to the end user. In order to provide a uniform way of communication at the application layer between the various sources and sinks of data, OPC-based interfaces are developed and deployed at each individual process unit.

Figure 27: Partial overview of CERTH/CPERIs shop floor and plants

Figure 28: CERTH/CPERIs Monitoring and control HMIs

- **Pilot Plant 1 –Batch process**

A combined hydroprocessing pilot-plant, fractionation unit, auto-clave reactor, fuel accelerated aging unit, as well as analytical instruments for fuel quality control will be used as one of the Use Case of SatisFactory. Among the related infrastructure, there are both continuous and batch process units which are at presented operated and monitored online. As each unit has different operating and safety challenges, two of them will be used as case studies in this project, the small hydroprocessing pilot plant (VB01) as a continuous process unit and the vacuum fractionation unit (HyDis) as a batch process unit. The VB01 continuous hydroprocessing pilot plant consists of a feed system, a single-reactor system and a product separation system. The feed system effectively maintains constant feed quality and H₂-to-oil ratio via a liquid feed pump and a gas flow controller. The reactor system consists of a single fixed-bed reactor with six independent heating zones, which sustain the desired temperature profile within the reactor. The reactor product passes through the product separation system, where it is first cooled via a cooling zone and then flashed via a High Pressure Low Temperature (HPLT) separator. It should also be noted that both feeds and products (gas and liquid) will be analysed within the CERTH/CPERI analytic laboratory equipped with state-of-the-art analytical instruments capable for all key fuel analysis. The operation of VB01 is enabled by a SCADA system that employs the total of 38 process variables associated with the unit via 17 control loops that are intended to maintain stable temperature, pressure, and flow rate within the reactor and feed/product lines.

Figure 29: Process Overview

One of the main operating challenges of the VB01 process unit is the varying operating conditions and feedstock types that are required when testing different feedstock and technologies. In particular, the system pressure may vary from 500 to 2000 psig, and the reactor temperature from 250 to 380°C. Moreover, feedstock that have been already utilized have different flow and composition characteristics. The wide operating window dictates the utilization of online and historical data as a database of local operating regions that will enable stable operation via setting the total of 17 control loops associated with it.

- **Pilot Plant 2 – Continuous Process**

A pilot plant that will be used for SatisFactory project is the SynGas unit of CERTH/CPERI-LPSDI. This pilot plant has been used for steam reforming and partial oxidation of methane and aqueous mixtures of hydrocarbons such as methanol and bio-oil. Catalytic partial oxidation of Methane can be an attractive process for converting natural gas to synthesis gas (SYNGAS), because it gives high methane conversions (over 90% per pass) combined with high selectivity to carbon monoxide. The unit supports a spout bed type reactor and a fixed bed reactor used alternatively for preliminary activity measurements. The pilot plant is fully automated and intuitive HMIs represent the alternative flow sheet of either reactor. The pilot plant unit is fully automated using a supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system. All system components (pumps, heaters, valves and so forth) are controlled by on/off commands or by pre-programmed start-up procedures. A remote monitoring system has been developed in order to provide real-time information regarding the state of the plant, as well as, trending features related to the evolution of the experiment runs. Among the objectives of the automation system, is the ability of the user to monitor the plant by utilizing a standard web browser base application and a secure information exchange framework.

Figure 30: Process Flow diagram of the Continuous Pilot Plant

- **Infrastructure related components**

Both pilot plants produce each day real-time data stored in repositories that provide a significant amount of information currently analysed using conventional tools while the decision making relies on information which is compiled in a manual manner by the process operators and the process supervisors. Besides the collection, analysis and deployment of automated actions, the aforementioned infrastructure is equipped with data visualization tools combined with content aware functions using diagnosis and alarm triggering tools. The user interacts with the devices, the sensors and the actuators through a set of user-friendly human machine interfaces (HMI) that provide the basis for the decision making process in real-time. Furthermore, the data can be accessed by local or remote information points and can be managed by supervisory functions. Thus, the operators can intuitively understand the status and the various conditions of the process equipment and respond accordingly upon demand. The aforementioned infrastructure is developed using a set of adaptive user interfaces combined with flexible sensor topologies that are able to tackle the heterogeneity of the various devices which are present in a smart factory.

The pilot plants are fully automated and controlled by a SCADA system with intuitive HMIs that represent the alternative flow sheet of either reactor. All system components (pumps, heaters, valves and so forth) are controlled by on/off commands or by pre-programmed start-up procedures. A remote monitoring system is present that provides real-time information regarding the state of the plant, as well as, trending features related to the evolution of the experiment runs. The SCADA system allows the operators to monitor the plant by utilizing a standard web browser based application and a secure information exchange framework.

Figure 31: Knowledge sharing from the signal data to actionable knowledge

3.2.2.2 Actors & stakeholders

- **Floor manager**

The floor manager has the general supervision on the workflow of the shop floor. He also makes integration decision support for allocation of resources at existing processes. He/she must have good knowledge on chemical processes, administrative skills and knowledge on management of human resources.

- **Process supervisor**

The process supervisor is responsible for the general operation of a pilot plant. He/she shares information with all involved actors about daily experiments and processes the data from the field and the laboratory analysis. He/she also schedules new constructions or system revamps. He/she must have administrative skills, experience on chemical processes, excellent knowledge of the operation of the pilot plant and good knowledge on using process monitoring systems.

- **Maintenance manager**

The maintenance manager is responsible of organising scheduled tasks on the shop floor. He/she is also involved on new constructions or system revamps scheduling and is informed about existing work progress and involvement of the technical team. He/she must have collaboration skills and automation, electrical and mechanical knowledge.

- **Maintenance supervisor**

The maintenance supervisor is responsible to coordinate the members of the technical team. He/she has collaboration with the maintenance manager, the process supervisors and the technical team in order to organize the scheduled and sudden actions. He/she must be in place to take immediate decisions when is needed. His/her collaboration with other stakeholders must be very good. Human resources management and automation, electrical and mechanical knowledge are mandatory.

- **Process technician**

The main task of process technicians is to support and maintain the operation of the pilot plants. He must be able to use various machine shop tools and he must have good knowledge of mechanical design software.

- **Control, automation, IT technician**

The maintenance of IT and automation structures is the main concern of this category of actors. They are also involved in new constructions and revamps. Experience on SCADA and automation software as well as IT infrastructure knowledge are required for this position.

- **Electrical technician**

Electrical technicians support the operation of pilot plants. They are involved in new constructions and revamps and preserve information related to performed procedures. They must have good knowledge and experience on high and low voltage electrical systems and must be able to understand electrical schematics and manuals.

- **Process operator**

Process operators perform daily actions regarding the operation of pilot plants. They report about malfunctions of abnormal behaviour of the operation and organise raw materials for the experiments. They have collaboration with process supervisors and with the members of the technical team.

3.2.2.3 *Progress beyond first iteration in CERTH/CPERI use-cases*

The period since the submission of the first iteration of D1.1 was very critical because there had to be the beginning of the implementation at the shop floor. At that time, there was only theoretical design and several requirements that the use cases had to cover. The first action that took place at CPERI shop floor was to look again at the use cases and discuss them with the actors that would participate at the project and were involved at the Business Scenarios. The first result from those discussions was that several requirements (SAFA requirements posted on JIRA) have been revised. The following table includes a list with all the requirements that refer at CPERI and have been revised since the first iteration of D1.1:

Table 1 : List of revised SAFA requirements of CPERI shop floor.

Req #	Key	Summary
1	SAFA-4	The HMIs of the platform shall be attractive and easy to use
2	SAFA-13	The tools and applications must be 24/7 operational
3	SAFA-17	The tools shall be able to successfully exchange data with the existing infrastructure at the shop floors
4	SAFA-18	SatisFactory tools shall give detailed description of selected maintenance actions
6	SAFA-24	SatisFactory components must have a successful and continuous data exchange with CIDEM
7	SAFA-27	Accurate detection of incidents
8	SAFA-31	Successful integration of all heterogeneous devices of the shop floors
9	SAFA-32	Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) shall be provided to the workers
10	SAFA-33	The platform of SatisFactory must enhance remote support and maintenance for the shop floors
11	SAFA-34	The system shall be able to monitoring actors through privacy preserving sensors
12	SAFA-37	The platform should present training procedures through multimedia content
13	SAFA-40	Depending on the SOP, some steps of the training activity shall be automatically verified
14	SAFA-41	All shop floor data must be stored in a common database
15	SAFA-55	The system shall be able to detect both pro-active and re-active incidents at the shop floor
16	SAFA-58	The AR components of SatisFactory must have continuous access to the database
17	SAFA-59	The platform shall support social communication between actors
18	SAFA-62	Gamification tools will be interactive with the actors
19	SAFA-65	AR tools will have the ability to interpret the displaying operating procedures
20	SAFA-66	Multi-Layered Description of Operating Procedures (OP-MLD) Real-time Ready
21	SAFA-67	The platform will allow uncoupling of Multi-Layered Description of operating procedures and their Interactive Real-time Visualization
22	SAFA-69	The symbols/terminology of the data presented on the glasses must be effective and easy to understand
23	SAFA-73	Continuous and successful data transfer between glasses and the database of each shop floor
24	SAFA-75	The frame of the glasses shall be optimal for the workers
27	SAFA-93	Alarms shall be accompanied with a description
28	SAFA-101	Different opinions shall be exchanged during the operation of a task
29	SAFA-105	The system shall provide means of submitting suggestions for

SATISFACTORY

		improvements available, in order to contribute to modernisation and overall improvement of working conditions
30	SAFA-107	The system shall utilize skills and capabilities of the workers available for optimal work assignment
31	SAFA-108	The system shall improve teamwork through optimal task allocation
32	SAFA-117	The system shall support inter-change of best practices between departments and units
33	SAFA-118	The product shall provide means to teach co-workers
34	SAFA-120	The communication product shall be open for non work related content
35	SAFA-131	Competition shall be informal and friendly
36	SAFA-132	The product shall not restrict workers' autonomy
37	SAFA-133	The system shall have access to the most recent work schedules
38	SAFA-134	The system shall be able to be adapted to different shifts
39	SAFA-135	The system shall not influence workers' carefulness
40	SAFA-136	The system shall be applicable when workers wear a mask
41	SAFA-137	Support flexible deviations from plan
42	SAFA-140	Support mobile users
43	SAFA-143	Support feedback answers on suggestions for improvement
44	SAFA-146	Release answers/feedback on suggestions for improvements to operators
45	SAFA-148	Human-Resources toolkit shall efficient manage idle times
46	SAFA-149	The system should be able to manage all the open tasks
47	SAFA-154	Continuous access to training procedures
48	SAFA-171	All tasks should have priority and criticality ranks
49	SAFA-172	The system shall be able to combine the heterogeneous acquired data from the shop floor
50	SAFA-174	Continuous update of the operators' skills
52	SAFA-178	Installation and troubleshooting of the system shall not require training beyond IT network administration and maintenance
53	SAFA-181	No frequencies, physical media, and protocols will be used for communication that interfere with existing communication systems at the factory
55	SAFA-186	The measurement units for the dimensions of the parts of the system shall match the units common in the deployment country
56	SAFA-187	Measurements, events, logs, and all shop floor dynamic shall be in the time zone of the deployment country
57	SAFA-189	HMI tool (on Mobile device) could be used to take photos from the working area
58	SAFA-192	Association of the workers' names with their suggestions
59	SAFA-193	Time duration availability of the suggestions
60	SAFA-197	UIs shall be in the formal language of the deployment country
61	SAFA-198	All UI interaction parts should be clearly visible
62	SAFA-200	The UIs should be user-friendly

63	SAFA-202	Suggestions will be sorted by submission date
64	SAFA-203	Suggestions filtering support
65	SAFA-204	Personal statistics available to the users
66	SAFA-205	Evaluation of a contribution will support point scale
67	SAFA-206	The product shall keep the prize detail separate from the system
68	SAFA-207	Suggestions system should support suggestion categories
69	SAFA-208	Open suggestions shall be sent to the decision makers
70	SAFA-211	The suggestion submission form shall be in similar format as the preexisting manual system
71	SAFA-215	Gamification must be presented in several subcomponents of satisfactory
72	SAFA-217	The gamification framework must support PBL
73	SAFA-218	No participant of the gamification shall be exposed as loser
74	SAFA-220	Other SatisFactory components shall submit points of participants to the gamification framework
75	SAFA-221	The gamification framework should allow workers to participate individually as well as in teams
76	SAFA-222	All urgent tasks shall be properly allocated to the employees
77	SAFA-223	Current location of employee shall be taken into account by the RA & HR workload balancing tool
78	SAFA-224	The system should be able to interface existing measurement tools and infrastructure
79	SAFA-225	All historical data from the shop-floor shall be available through CIDEM
80	SAFA-226	All information exchanged and stored within SatisFactory components shall be in a common format understandable from all components
81	SAFA-227	Timely workers notification in case of an alarm
82	SAFA-228	The UI shall provide maps visualization for a more concrete understanding
83	SAFA-229	The messages provided by the system shall be clear and easy to understand
84	SAFA-230	The SatisFactory components shall be able to store and retrieve large amounts of data

Several revisions have been made at the BSCs and the UCs of SatisFactory as well. The feedback from the actors was used for these revisions as well as the discussions between the end-users and the technology providing partners. Regarding the BSCs, new restrictions, prerequisites and needs came up and all of them were included at the second iteration of the Deliverable D1.2. Most of the Use Cases were also revised, some were deleted and some new came up. The complete revised descriptions of the UCs are presented at the second iteration of the Deliverable D1.2.

3.2.3 *SUNLIGHT – Batteries discrete manufacturing*

3.2.3.1 *Process*

Sunlight will involve three manufacturing processes related with three different production lines. The first one is the jar formation process which is the last stage of the PzS batteries production line. The second one is Motive power (traction) batteries assembly line and third one is the manual assembly line of the OPzS and OpzV batteries.

- **Jar Formation Process**

The initial formation charge of a lead-acid battery, whether in the form of plates or as an already assembled battery, is quite a complex bundle of chemical reactions. It is important to know in principle about the most important parameters controlling this process in order to achieve good reproducible results with reasonable efforts.

Jar formation is applied to already assembled batteries. The formation process for the batteries cells begins with the filling process. The time gap between electrolyte filling and the initiation of the formation process must be considered very carefully. If batteries are put into formation immediately after filling, a significant amount of acid may remain unreacted. There are several Formation algorithms and profiles that can be applied. Several conditions must be considered for applying the most proper formation profile.

Figure 32: Jar formation

- **Motive power (Traction) battery assembly**

Sunlight Motive power batteries can cover all types of motive power needs, from light duty single-shift operation to heavy duty multi-shift operations, and are suitable for all industrial electric forklift types, such as counterbalanced, narrow aisle and hand trucks.

The Motive Power battery assembly procedure includes the following stages:

- Cells fitting into metal tray
- Inspection level electrolyte
- Battery cleaning
- Connectors fitting
- Inspection bolts and voltage
- Labels fitting
- Advisories & appurtenances fitting
- Palletizing & packing with nylon

Figure 33: Sunlight Motive Power Battery

Figure 34: Sunlight Motive Power Battery Assembly line

- **OPzS and OPzV battery manual assembly**

OPzS and OPzV batteries are characterized by their long life span, durability under cyclic use conditions as well as for their low maintenance requirements, providing you a cost effective energy solution. Their robust construction, the high quality raw materials used for their production in addition to their optimum design - according to DIN international standards, enhance their capacity and performance.

OPzS and OPzV batteries are assembled manually. The assembly production line includes the following processes:

- Plate cropping and brushing
- Block stacking
- Poles and strap welding
- Battery cell assembly
- Lid gluing
- Electrolyte filling
- Battery Activation
- Cleaning
- Labelling
- Packing

Figure 35: OPzS & OPzV Manual Assembly line

Actors & stakeholders

- **Operators**

Operators are operating the machines or assembling batteries on the shop floor. They are monitoring the production process and carrying out basic testing and quality checks. They are cleaning and maintaining work areas and machinery. They may also supervise Trainees during the working day.

- **Trainees**

Trainees are not experienced operators who have been working at a factory's workplace less than six months and thus are getting trained.

- **Foreman or Operations Supervisor**

Operations Supervisors are highly experienced workers with a very good knowledge of the machines and good understanding of the work processes. They are responsible for training of new workers (Trainees). They spend about 90% of their working time on the shop floor. Their main responsibilities are Coordinate daily production floor activities and delegate assignments to production personnel.

- **Mechanical Technicians and Electricians**

Mechanical Technicians and Electricians are part of the Technical team and are responsible for new installations, Troubleshooting and maintenance of the infrastructure.

Installing new machinery or equipment, the Mechanical technicians are responsible for the mechanical installations and assembly of the mechanical part. The Electricians are responsible for the cabling and all the necessary electrical and electronic connections that will make the machine workable.

- **Production Plant Manager**

The Production Plant Manager controls and coordinates the manufacturing processes. He maintain optimum operation by assigning workers, keeping work and production schedules, collecting and looking through data to find places of waste or places of improvement, keep an eye on worker safety and plant safety.

- **Production Planner**

Production Planner plans and prepares production schedules for manufacture of the products: Draws up master schedule to establish sequence and lead time of each operation to meet shipping dates according to sales forecasts or customer orders.

- **Production Supervisors**

Production Supervisor completes production plan by scheduling and assigning personnel, accomplishing work results, establishing priorities, monitoring progress, revising schedules, resolving problem, reporting results of the processing flow on shift production summaries.

- **Maintenance Manager**

Maintenance manager primary responsibilities are management, maintenance and construction of manufacturing facilities, associated infrastructure and manufacturing equipment. He manages the staff, processes and activities for maintaining all plant machinery to ensure safe, continual and efficient operation.

3.2.3.2 *Progress beyond first iteration in SUNLIGHT use-case*

It has been done a lot of progress since the initial submission of the deliverable D1.1. The requirements that has been derived from the actor's interviews have been transformed to Business Scenario's. It was decided which of the discussed Business Scenarios will be implemented in cooperation with the involved partners. The implementation of them has been started but it is still in an early stage. The discussions with the actors that have been initially interviewed have been repeated in the time period after the first iteration of the D1.1. The requirements that have been created for Sunlight in the JIRA platform has been reviewed. A new requirement has been created, some of them has been set 'out of scope' and some others has been updated. The total list of the requirements that is related with Sunlight and has been reviewed during this period are presented in the following table.

Table 2 : List of reviewed SAFA requirements of Sunlight shop floor.

Req. #	Key	Summary
1	SAFA-4	The HMIs of the platform shall be attractive and easy to use
2	SAFA-13	The tools and applications must be 24/7 operational
3	SAFA-17	The tools shall be able to succesfully exchange data with the existing

		infrastructure at the shop floors
4	SAFA-18	SatisFactory tools shall give detailed description of selected maintenance actions
5	SAFA-19	The platform will include a personal protection equipment usage reminder
6	SAFA-24	SatisFactory components must have a successful and continuous data exchange with CIDEM
7	SAFA-27	Accurate detection of incidents
8	SAFA-31	Successful integration of all heterogeneous devices of the shop floors
9	SAFA-32	Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) shall be provided to the workers
10	SAFA-33	The platform of SatisFactory must enhance remote support and maintenance for the shop floors
11	SAFA-34	The system shall be able to monitoring actors through privacy preserving sensors
12	SAFA-37	The platform should present training procedures through multimedia content
13	SAFA-40	Depending on the SOP, some steps of the training activity shall be automatically verified
14	SAFA-41	All shop floor data must be stored in a common database
15	SAFA-55	The system shall be able to detect both pro-active and re-active incidents at the shop floor
16	SAFA-58	The AR components of SatisFactory must have continuous access to the database
17	SAFA-59	The platform shall support social communication between actors
18	SAFA-62	Gamification tools will be interactive with the actors
19	SAFA-65	AR tools will have the ability to interpret the displaying operating procedures
20	SAFA-66	Multi-Layered Description of Operating Procedures (OP-MLD) Real-time Ready
21	SAFA-67	The platform will allow uncoupling of Multi-Layered Description of operating procedures and their Interactive Real-time Visualization
22	SAFA-69	The symbols/terminology of the data presented on the glasses must be effective and easy to understand
23	SAFA-73	Continuous and successful data transfer between glasses and the database of each shop floor
24	SAFA-75	The frame of the glasses shall be optimal for the workers
25	SAFA-76	Real time and continuous monitoring of battery cell temperature during the procedure of Jar formation
26	SAFA-79	Real-time incident detection during Jar formation of batteries' cells
27	SAFA-93	Alarms shall be accompanied with a description
28	SAFA-101	Different opinions shall be exchanged during the operation of a task
29	SAFA-105	The system shall provide means of submitting suggestions for improvements available, in order to contribute to modernization and

SATISFACTORY

		overall improvement of working conditions
30	SAFA-107	The system shall utilize skills and capabilities of the workers available for optimal work assignment
31	SAFA-108	The system shall improve teamwork through optimal task allocation
32	SAFA-117	The system shall support inter-change of best practices between departments and units
33	SAFA-118	The product shall provide means to teach co-workers
34	SAFA-120	The communication product shall be open for non work related content
35	SAFA-131	Competition shall be informal and friendly
36	SAFA-132	The product shall not restrict workers' autonomy
37	SAFA-133	The system shall have access to the most recent work schedules
38	SAFA-134	The system shall be able to be adapted to different shifts
39	SAFA-135	The system shall not influence workers' carefulness
40	SAFA-136	The system shall be applicable when workers wear a mask
41	SAFA-137	Support flexible deviations from plan
42	SAFA-140	Support mobile users
43	SAFA-143	Support feedback answers on suggestions for improvement
44	SAFA-146	Release answers/feedback on suggestions for improvements to operators
45	SAFA-148	Human-Resources toolkit shall efficient manage idle times
46	SAFA-149	The system should be able to manage all the open tasks
47	SAFA-154	Continuous access to training procedures
48	SAFA-171	All tasks should have priority and criticality ranks
49	SAFA-172	The system shall be able to combine the heterogeneous acquired data from the shop floor
50	SAFA-174	Continuous update of the operators' skills
51	SAFA-176	The system shall provide efficient means for instructing workers on the necessary assembly parts of a battery belonging to an order and necessary actions at each step of the assembly procedure
52	SAFA-178	Installation and troubleshooting of the system shall not require training beyond IT network administration and maintenance
53	SAFA-181	No frequencies, physical media, and protocols will be used for communication that interfere with existing communication systems at the factory
54	SAFA-184	The connectors, screws, and other electromechanical elements of the system shall match with the standard types used in the country where the factory is located
55	SAFA-186	The measurement units for the dimensions of the parts of the system shall match the units common in the deployment country
56	SAFA-187	Measurements, events, logs, and all shop floor dynamic shall be in the time zone of the deployment country
57	SAFA-189	HMI tool (on Mobile device) could be used to take photos from the working area
58	SAFA-192	Association of the workers' names with their suggestions

59	SAFA-193	Time duration availability of the suggestions
60	SAFA-197	UIs shall be in the formal language of the deployment country
61	SAFA-198	All UI interaction parts should be clearly visible
62	SAFA-200	The UIs should be user-friendly
63	SAFA-202	Suggestions will be sorted by submission date
64	SAFA-203	Suggestions filtering support
65	SAFA-204	Personal statistics available to the users
66	SAFA-205	Evaluation of a contribution will support point scale
67	SAFA-206	The product shall keep the prize detail separate from the system
68	SAFA-207	Suggestions system should support suggestion categories
69	SAFA-208	Open suggestions shall be sent to the decision makers
70	SAFA-211	The suggestion submission form shall be in similar format as the preexisting manual system
71	SAFA-215	Gamification must be presented in several subcomponents of satisfactory
72	SAFA-217	The gamification framework must support PBL
73	SAFA-218	No participant of the gamification shall be exposed as loser
74	SAFA-220	Other SatisFactory components shall submit points of participants to the gamification framework
75	SAFA-221	The gamification framework should allow workers to participate individually as well as in teams
76	SAFA-222	All urgent tasks shall be properly allocated to the employees
77	SAFA-223	Current location of employee shall be taken into account by the RA & HR workload balancing tool
78	SAFA-224	The system should be able to interface existing measurement tools and infrastructure
79	SAFA-225	All historical data from the shop-floor shall be available through CIDEM
80	SAFA-226	All information exchanged and stored within SatisFactory components shall be in a common format understandable from all components
81	SAFA-227	Timely workers notification in case of an alarm
82	SAFA-228	The UI shall provide maps visualization for a more concrete understanding
83	SAFA-229	The messages provided by the system shall be clear and easy to understand
84	SAFA-230	The SatisFactory components shall be able to store and retrieve large amounts of data

The derived BSCs and the UCs has been updated accordingly in the second iteration of the Deliverable D1.2.

3.2.4 ATLANTIS – Maintenance operations

3.2.4.1 Process

Atlantis develops and implements solutions in the field of electromechanical equipment maintenance, asset management and industrial production.

In the SatisFactory project, the main effort of Atlantis will be devoted to the development and implementation of innovative applications for decision support for maintenance purposes, in order to be applied to the industrial sectors.

3.2.4.2 Actors & stakeholders

- **Maintenance Manager**

The Maintenance Manager directs and manages the plant maintenance staff, programs and processes, typically under the direction of the plant operations manager or production manager, in order to ensure safe, timely and efficient operation of all plant machinery and equipment. He/She plans the procedure to be applied on the shop-floor, defines and develops maintenance strategies, policies and criteria for performance, according to the company strategies. The Maintenance Manager defines the organizational model of maintenance, the processes and tools to support the tasks. Moreover, he/she ensures the levels of availability, reliability, maintainability, supportability, safety and quality required for the entire useful life of assets, while staying within the budget.

- **Maintenance Supervisor**

The Maintenance Supervisor is the connection between the management and the actual performance of the tasks. He/She is directly responsible for overseeing the efforts of maintenance workers who install, repair or service property or machinery. He/She plans the maintenance tasks within his/her area of responsibility. The Maintenance Supervisor organizes, manages and develops the maintenance resources: personnel, materials and equipment; while ensuring compliance with regulations and procedures related to safety, health and environment. Moreover, he/she participates in the technical aspects of contracts and procurement process and manage the performance of the contractors and communicates to all necessary partners like staff, contractors, customers and suppliers.

- **Maintenance Coordinator**

In some plants, there is a Maintenance Coordinator, who acts under the Maintenance Manager (or Supervisor, depending on the size of the plant), in terms of organizing and coordinating the maintenance tasks. This role is more 'administrative', helping communicating tasks from the Supervisor to the Technicians.

- **Maintenance Technician**

The Maintenance Technician is the person that receives directions and has the technical knowledge and skills to implement the tasks assigned to him/her by the Supervisor (or Manager, if there is no Supervisor). He/She performs or ensures proper execution according to rules and procedures relating to safety, health and environmental protection. He/she acts promptly in case of failure or malfunction, ensuring the effectiveness of the restoration. The Maintenance Technician ensures the availability of materials, tools and equipment necessary for the execution of maintenance tasks and is also the one using or ensuring the usage of ICT systems.

3.2.4.3 *Progress beyond first iteration in MAINTENANCE use-case*

To further understand the specific needs of the end-users, a series of web meetings have been conducted in the period since the first iteration. The main focus has been set on the pre-pilot environment at CERTH/CPERI, where the solutions under development are going to be first deployed. The role of the specific actors at the CERTH/CPERI shop floor were further analysed and this has been translated into requirements for the maintenance related SatisFactory architectural components. The aim was to deepen the requirement analysis and to re-evaluate the associated requirements and thus to affect the development of the corresponding tools and plans. The procedure has been successful and it will be employed in the next period too at CERTH/CPERI, as well as in the Industrial Pilots at SUNLIGHT and COMAU, where the first iteration of the deployment starts in M22.

4. END-USERS REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

This chapter briefly introduces the process adopted to collect the user requirements, conducted through face-to-face interviews in the premises of the three considered industrial sectors: automotive machinery, battery production and chemical process. Following an analysis of these interviews is presented.

4.1 REQUIREMENTS COLLECTION PROCESS

SatisFactory end-users have been actively involved in the requirements collection. A total of 41 interviews has been performed, 18 to CERTH resources, 15 of them to Comau employees, and finally 8 to Sunlight personnel.

The questionnaire is composed by 40 queries organized in eight sections, respectively:

- Section 1 – Company general information, containing general questions regarding the organization figures;
- Section 2 – Actor/Stakeholder general information, which includes requests about experience, know-how and role of the interviewed person;
- Section 3 – Activities/Work description, asking details about involved process and workplace;
- Section 4 – Employees turnover, with requests on job recruiting process;
- Section 5 – Training received , regarding the way the actual job was learned and training needs;
- Section 6 – Procedures and guidelines applied (plus IT support), to collect information on the IT enabling environment to be used at workplace level and documents/procedures accessed;
- Section 7 – Working scenario improvement, containing questions about possible enhancements of the working environment;
- Section 8 – Other suggestions

The questionnaire template is attached to this document as "*Annex 1 – Interview notes and template*".

Each interview lasted approximately 1 hour and provided good feedbacks and suggestions for the SatisFactory Project developments. Generally, the interviewed people answered to all the questions: only sometimes problems of confidentiality or of lack of information arise. Due to privacy

company rules and the distribution level of this document, only aggregated data at use-case level will be presented. In "Annex 5 – Informed Consent For Interviews" a consent letter form is presented.

In the following sections the main achievements from the interview process are described for the three industrial sectors considered.

4.1.1.1 Progress beyond first iteration in Requirements collection process

The Interviews performed at Sunlight and COMAU in November and January helped with creating a better understanding of the domain and its requirements. In particular, the new requirements that were discovered had to do with how the system's interface should be built and how the system could better mesh with the work processes at factories. It appears also that the anonymity features of the system need to be rethought, so as to make them useful both in cases where anonymity is desired and in cases where workers are indeed compensated for their suggestions.

4.2 REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

4.2.1 COMAU - Automotive discrete manufacturing

The personnel interviewed by COMAU have been selected according to three different criteria:

- Application environment (Robot wrist assembly, Welding guns assembly, Welding lines assembly);
- Company role (Process operator, Team leader, Design & ergonomics engineer);
- Years of experience in the role .

In order to proceed with the collection of contributions from the experts, a formal procedure of authorization requests has been followed. COMAU management was involved to validate the interview process, in particular, the Engineering and Quality Vice-President, the Human Resources office, the Legal office and the Manufacturing responsible.

For confidentiality and privacy reasons only aggregated data will be presented in the following.

At the end of the COMAU interviews round a total of 15 experts was interviewed. All interviews have been performed face-to-face in COMAU meeting rooms or directly in shop-floor environment. Final percentage of answered question was about 95,2%.

Out of the 15 interviewed persons, 4 experts belong to the Robotics area and in particular to the robot wrist assembly, 5 specialists come from the body welding area and specifically from the welding gun assembly area; finally 6 experts belong to the body welding lines assembly operations.

Considering their role in COMAU, the 15 interviewed are clustered as 7 Process operators, 4 Technical leaders and 4 Design & ergonomics engineers, as represented in the following diagram.

Figure 36: COMAU stakeholders applications & roles

A different parameter used to classify the actors was regarding their education level. The results are presented in the figure below. It is possible to see that the three figures selected (Opertors, Technical Leaders, Designers) well reflect on the education degree, with 1 third that has vocational degree, 1 third Bachelor and 1 third Master degree.

Figure 37: COMAU actors and stakeholders' education level

Considering the experience in the role, 5 interviewed have till 5 years of knowledge, 6 are in the range between 5 to 20 years, and finally, 4 have more than 20 years of experience.

Figure 38: COMAU stakeholders years of experience in the role

With respect to the question 2.5 of the questionnaire: "Which are your main areas of expertise?"

The following result, presented in the figure below, has been achieved: main competence areas are in the mechanics, followed by electrical & software, and project & process management.

Figure 39: COMAU Technological areas of expertise

Another interesting point raised up from the questionnaires results is how COMAU employees came to their actual working position. As depicted in the picture below, most of the actors came internally from different FIAT Group companies. The other different entries like University, stages, suppliers, other employees and labor office are well balanced

Figure 40: How COMAU actors came to this job

With respect to the safety issues, that play a key role in the manufacturing shop-floor, and in the workplace, question 3.5 of the questionnaire: “Do you use any specific safety device?” aimed to quantify the usage of personal protective equipment by the experts. All the in 15 interviewed use foot/leg protections (i.e. Safety shoes) when they are in the shop-floor, while respectively 10 and 9 use hand and eye protections (safety gloves and safety glasses). Finally only 4 perform activities requiring body protections (safety belts).

Figure 41: Personal Protective Equipment (OSHA classification)

The graph presented in the figure above, is strictly connected to the fact that quite all the interviewed actors spend some of the working-time in the manufacturing shop-floor. This is confirmed by the picture below.

Figure 42: COMAU actors' workplace

With reference to “Section 4 – Employees turnover” and in particular to question “How many years do you think people stay in the company on average?”, the analysis highlights that more than 70% of the interviewed feels that the team in which they operate has a low turnover. This is represented in the following figure.

Figure 43: Personnel Turnover

With reference to Section 5, and more precisely to question “How would you train someone to do your job? Or, how would you have wished to be trained?”, the 47% of the interviewed employees prefers a formal training including training on the job, the 40% prefers a formal training and the remaining 13% prefers a more direct approach with only training on the job.

It is interesting to remark that process operators, that normally receive only training on the job would like to receive also formal trainings with more theoretical concepts.

Figure 44: Personnel wished training

Final question related to the degree of satisfaction of the actual workplace for the interviewed experts. It was asked them to provide a value between 1 and 10 where 1 was the least satisfaction level and 10 was the maximum. The 15 answers obtained were in the range 5 to 9, thus in order to simplify the reading, they have been clustered in 4 groups, respectively 5-6 (3 answers), 7 (5 answers), 8 (6 answers) and, finally 9 (1 answer). The following diagram shows the percentages of these results.

Figure 45: Overall Workplace satisfaction degree

4.2.2 CERTH – Chemical continuous process

These results refer to the eighteen (18) actors that were interviewed within CERTH. The criteria that used for the selection of the employees to be interviewed based on the fact that we should choose actors from all the categories we have. Thus, we chose:

- 6 process operators (from 2 pilot plants)
- 9 technicians (4 Automation / IT technicians, 3 process technicians and 2 electrical technicians)
- 3 supervisors (floor manager, process supervisor, maintenance supervisor)

The following diagram shows the above categories:

Figure 46: CERTH actors' categories

The interview procedure carried out with no problems. Actors showed great interest and were willing to answer most of the questions because they thought it is an opportunity to improve several problems regarding their daily actions.

We separate actors considering their experience in their roles and we found that the majority (9 actors) is between 5 to 20 years, 5 of the actors have 5 and less years of experience and 4 of them are very experienced, with more than 20 years at their jobs. The following diagram presents these results.

Figure 47: CERTH actors' years of experience

Another way to separate actors was regarding their education level. The results are presented in the above figure. We can point out that only 6% of the actors have vocational education, in contrast with a 55% with masters or PhD degree. This means that most of CERTH's employees are highly educated.

Figure 48: CERTH actors' education level

Trying to find out the areas of expertise of the actors (question 2.5 of the questionnaire), we created the next figure. The main competence areas seem to be the pilot plant operation and the electrical and automation areas. This seems reasonable since most of the interviewed actors were process operators or technicians. Biofuels and renewable energy area follows, which is also reasonable because of the areas that CERTH deals with.

Figure 49: CERTH actors' areas of expertise

Another very interesting point that came out of the results of the questionnaires is how CERTH actors came to their current job. As we can see at the next figure, most of the actors came as students (internship or bachelor thesis) first and after that they were hired as employees. This means that CERTH has a very good collaboration with education institutes (universities, technological schools) and they try to invest on people who begin their careers and have fresh ideas and lot of energy.

Figure 50: How CERTH actors came to this job

Referring to the 3.2 question of the questionnaire, we can see where actors spend their working hours. From the eighteen employees that were interviewed, 100% of them answered that spends some time at the shop floor. We can also see that all actors have their own office. The other places, like the machine shop or the laboratories, are used from some of the actors depending from their activities.

Figure 51: CERTH actors' workplace

Question 3.5 of the questionnaire refers to safety equipment that is used at CERTH facilities. Actors' safety has a critical role at CERTH because working conditions inside the shop floor area are dangerous and unhealthy. All actors, depending on their role, must use safety equipment in order not to expose themselves into any danger. As we can see at the next figure, most of the actors use safety glasses, working apron and safety gloves. Some of them use safety masks, while others use safety shoes and helmet.

Figure 52: CERTH actors' safety equipment usage

With reference to "Section 4 – Employees turnover" of the questionnaire and in particular to question "How many years do you think people stay in the company on average?", it seems clearly that actors of CERTH are satisfied from their jobs. Almost 80% of the actors stay at this job more than 10 years, with almost half of them for all their careers and only about 15% stay less than a decade.

Figure 53: CERTH actors' turnover

With reference to “Section 5” and more precisely to question “How would you train someone to do your job? Or, how would you have wished to be trained?” the results that are presented at the next figure are very interesting. Most supervisors and process operators believe that theoretical training must be the first issue and practice must follow. In the contrary, most of the technicians would train a new employee by having him all day along them showing how actions must be performed.

Another issue we can point from the diagram is that some of the technicians and the process operators were very satisfied with their training and they would perform the same to a new colleague.

Figure 54: CERTH actors’ wished training

The result from “Section 4” (Figure 55) about actor’s turnover is being verified from the answers at question 7.5, which was asking from actors to evaluate their workplace. 72% of the actors rated with 8 or higher (from 1-10, 10 being the best) the workspace at CERTH which means that they think it is quite good.

Figure 55: CERTH actors' overall workplace satisfaction degree

4.2.3 *SUNLIGHT – Batteries discrete manufacturing*

Six (6) actors have been interviewed within Systems Sunlight. The employees have been chosen from different departments and they have been classified as following:

- 1 operator (from the maintenance department)
- 1 foreman (from the Jar formation department)
- 2 production supervisors (battery production, formation department)
- 1 factory production manager
- 1 maintenance manager

The results of the interviews presented in the following diagrams:

Figure 56: Sunlight actors' categories

The interviews have been performed smoothly. The actors didn't hesitate to answer to any question. Most of them provide us a lot of information by having with us an open discussion.

Some of the actors are very experienced while some others are new in the company. No one has an experience of more than 20 years. Three of them have less than 5 years and the rest of the actors have an experience between 5 and 20 years. The following diagram presents the results:

Figure 57: Sunlight actors' years of experience

All the actors that have been interviewed have technical education. All of them are involved with mechanics and some of them with electrical, IT technology and automation.

Two thirds of the interviewers have a bachelor degree while half of them have also a master degree. The rest of the actors have technical education.

Figure 58: Sunlight actors' education

Figure 59: Sunlight actors' areas of expertise

Actors have been asked how did they came to work in Sunlight. It is very important that most of them have been suggested or informed by others. This denotes that people (working in Sunlight or not) have a good opinion about the company and they can easily advise others to work in Sunlight. A significant presentence answered that they found the job through Networking.

Figure 60: How Sunlight actors' found this job

Actors have been also asked to describe where their workplace is. Most of them have answered that they work both in the shop floor and the office. Some of them are working only in office. Technicians can be in any place in the factory since that they maintain all the machinery and the equipment.

Figure 61: SUNLIGHT actors' workplace

Sunlight is a chemical factory and the use of safety equipment within the several shop floors is mandatory. Factory personnel are well trained and aware of the relevant safety procedures. This is also confirmed by the diagram shown below, where the use of safety equipment such as Uniforms, Glasses, gloves, safety shoes and safety masks, is reported:

Figure 62: Sunlight actors' safety equipment usage

Sunlight actors seem to be satisfied from their jobs because in the question: "How many years do you think people stay in the company on average?", most of them answered that they stay for more than 7 years.

Figure 63: Sunlight actors' turnover

By analysing the answers to the question "How would you train someone to do your job? Or, how would you have wished to be trained?" the results shows that most of them prefer theoretical training together with practical training in the production line.

Figure 64: Sunlight actors' wished training

The actors were asking also to evaluate their workplace. The result shows that they are satisfied since that 83% rated the workplace with 7 and 17% with 8.

Figure 65: Sunlight overall workplace satisfaction degree

4.2.4 Interviews Report

4.2.4.1 SUNLIGHT Interviews 02-03 November report

The interviews at SUNLIGHT were conducted keeping in mind that users should be selected from different categories. Although the number of users were kept to four (4), it was made sure that the selection criteria covers all concerned aspects. The users belong to the following categories with respect to their job descriptions:

- Worker
- Foreman
- Mechanical Engineer

Figure 66: SUNLIGHT User Selection w.r.t. Job Description

The selected users belonged to the following departments:

- Traction Battery Assembly
- R&D

Figure 67: SUNLIGHT User Selection w.r.t. Department

It was also kept into consideration that the selected users belong to different groups with respect to work experience. The work experience among the selected users varied from one (1) year to as high as five (5) years.

Figure 68: SUNLIGHT User Selection w.r.t. Work Experience (Years)

4.2.4.2 *COMAU Interviews 27-28 January report*

Five people were interviewed at COMAU. One was a worker, two engineers, one foreman, and one decision-maker in safety-related areas. The experience of the worker was 38 years. Both blue-collar personnel came from the assembly department.

5. KEY TOPICS AND REQUIREMENTS

After the analysis of all interviews conducted by the three end-users of the SatisFactory consortium and preliminary brainstorming performed by the four technology partners, an initial Volere requirements database has been filled.

This chapter presents in the first section an example of the key topics derived from industrial partners interviews, while in the second part an extract of the eighty-three (83) requirements contained in the Jira database is shown.

These project needs messages will be subject of further improvements, focusing in particular the adherence to project scope, duplications, priorities management and implementation phases. The results of this enhancement process will be reported in the new releases of the present Deliverable, expected by project month M14 and M26.

5.1 END-USERS KEY TOPICS

This section describes the key topics that represent the synthesis of the end-user needs, derived from the interview process performed in collaboration with personnel coming respectively from the three end-users environments: discrete manufacturing in automotive for COMAU, discrete manufacturing for batteries for SUNLIGHT and continuous process in chemical applications in CERTH labs. Due to privacy issues, only aggregated data is presented in the following sections.

This preliminary analysis allowed to identify the user-requirement areas that will serve as basis for the future SatisFactory implementations. This study has been conducted considering the benefits and improvement areas, as well as the potential weakness and attention fields.

5.1.1 Key topics from Comau interview process

This section summarizes the key topics highlighted during the interview process conducted in Comau. As described below many important messages refer to user needs as well as mandatory and nice to have requirements that could improve the manufacturing operations and the workplace organization, that will lead to an improved worker satisfaction. Some messages refer to potential concerns and areas of attention that must be considered during the project developments.

5.1.1.1 Benefits and improvement areas

1. IT HW/SW platforms provide a good support, to improve the operators access to engineering and manufacturing information and documents
2. IT offers an enabling technology to implement remote functionalities such as production support and remote maintenance
3. Innovative sensing and actuating technologies (IoT) offer a good basis for ergonomics parameters real-time monitoring of human operators (e.g.

accelerations, number of repetitive operations performed, strength required in specific operations, etc.)

4. Safety in the shop-floor can be improved by means of innovative sensing, with safety devices wearing verifications through RFIDs or WSN applications
5. A good support is offered by the innovative sensing on the activities planning, coordinating the resources in order to balance the daily workloads among a team of workers, e.g. planning heavy activities in the first part of the day and light ones in the last part of the shift
6. IT architecture provides an innovative training environment that allows multimedia training procedures and sessions
7. Some procedures require the use of both hands. In this case the use of other senses could be a good alternative. An example could be vocal guides
8. Workloads require that operators replace colleagues in their activities. They must have clear in mind the right Sequence of Operations, so an online guide that reminds the correct steps could avoid mistakes
9. The application of terminals that guide the operators during the production process could lead to assisted production processes that generate automatically reports and checklists according to the operations performed
10. The integration of all devices, like power tools, measuring systems (laser level), etc. could lead to the establishment of a common database where all production data could be managed
11. Manufacturing IT platforms should support planners to assign lighter workloads to elderly/handicapped employees

5.1.1.2 **Potential weakness and attention areas**

1. Introducing additional IT platform to guide the operators in their daily work activities could represent a potential risk of increasing their normal workload
2. A potential risk of limiting operators privacy is represented by the additional number of cameras and sensors that can track the activities and the time required to perform them
3. New IT environment shall be user-friendly
4. The introduction of new devices in addition to the existing ones means also the addition of activities for their maintenance
5. The introduction of new terminals could lead to the introduction of new training in order to let the people work with these new devices
6. For young people the addition of IT technology, could be interesting, while for more aged persons, could create problems

5.1.2 Key topics from CERTH/CPERI interview process

According to the most significant information gathered from the CERTH actors' interviews, the following list of key topics has been identified:

1. In general, all actors are satisfied with their work and they find it rather interesting
2. A lot of CERTH workers have spent most of their career years at this job so far. In general, people stay many years in this job
3. Almost everyone would recommend his/her friends/children to do the same work
4. Relationships and collaboration between workers are very good
5. Actors who are working most of their time at an office have better working conditions from those who spend more time at the shop floor
6. There is a big need for safety due to the nature of daily activities, therefore all workers use safety measures and would like to be informed about the incidents and the potential situations that might be present at the shop floor
7. There is some flexibility on how each worker manages his working time. It would be beneficial to have an electronic system for the tracking of the activities that will be updated dynamically and accessible to every employee
8. There are written procedures for some of the activities, but they should be more that what actually is available
9. Most of the employees receive many kinds of training regarding their working sections, but they feel the need of continuous training sessions. The field that CERTH is working on is very demanding and employees must always be aware for novel technologies
10. Fire and gas alarms are incidents that can occur. In this regard, a system for monitoring and notifying the status of the shop floor could be useful

5.1.3 Key topics from Sunlight interview process

Having a constructive discussion with the Sunlight interviewers, we have noted some useful conclusions.

1. All actors have the feeling that they are members of a serious company
2. Most of the interviewers are not thinking to seek for another job

3. Most of them are satisfied of their job and they would recommend to their friends/children to do the same work
4. There is a good teamwork between them and in case of a problem they try to solve it as a team
5. All of them are aware about safety issues and there is no doubt to use safety equipment
6. Most of the interviewers have a good relation between them and the meet each other in their free time
7. All of the actors are positive to attend any possible training and most of them are ready to perform training to their colleagues.

5.2 REQUIREMENTS AND USER NEEDS

In this section a detailed analysis regarding the collected requirements and user needs is provided, starting from the analysis described in previous section, that allowed to identify the user requirements key findings.

In particular the parameters analyzed in the following are:

- Number of Issues assigned to single person
- Issues Type (Requirement, user needs, etc.)
- Priority Level (Blocker, Critical, Major, Minor, Nice to have, Trivial)
- Issues status (Quality Check passed, Open, Part of specification, Out of scope, Duplicate)
- Issue creator (who entered the issues in the database)
- Issue Typology (Functional non-functional, etc.)

5.3 OVERALL ACTIVITY ON JIRA ISSUES

The following chart shows the number of issues **created** (227) vs. the number of issues **resolved** (97) since the beginning of the project, with a total of 86 requirements that passed the quality check, since first report publishing (M4). The list of these issues is attached in "Annex 6 – Issues from Jira Database".

5.4 JIRA ISSUES DETAILED ANALYSIS

The following Pie Chart report and related table show the total list of issues, grouped by assignee. However, more than one person has contributed to each issue, but JIRA can extract only the assigner and not all the persons associate with it. Thus, all partners, even they do not appeared in this diagram have been contributed to the requirements determination.

Figure 69: Total Issues per Assignee

Assignee	Project Partner	Issues	%
Marc Jentsch	FIT	78	34%
Stelios Krinidis	CERTH/ITI	46	20%
Pietro Cultrona	COMAU	18	7%
Chrysovalantou Ziogou	CERTH/CPERI	17	7%
Antonio Serra	REGOLA	16	7%
Symeon Parcharidis	SUNLIGHT	14	6%
Erion Elmasllari	FIT	9	3%
Francesco Sottile	ISMB	8	3%
Emiliano Della Casa	GLASSUP	7	3%
Sarah Suleri	FIT	6	2%

Sarah León Rojas	FIT	4	1%
Paolo Vergori	ISMB	2	0%
Stylios Zikos	CERTH/ITI	1	0%
Hassan Rasheed	ISMB	1	0%

The following Pie Chart and table report the total amount of database entries classified by Volere Requirements, User Needs and Development Requirements.

Figure 70: Total Issues grouped by type

Issue Type	Issues	%
Volere Requirement	169	74%
User Need	47	20%
Deployment Requirement	11	4%

In the following diagram and table the priority level of the issues composing the Satisfactory database is depicted.

Figure 71: Total Issues grouped by priority level

Priority Level	Issues	%
Major	153	67%
Critical	29	12%
Minor	18	7%
Blocker	15	6%
Nice to have	9	3%
Trivial	3	1%

The following pie chart reports the issues status, according to the evaluation process reported in Chapter 2.

Figure 72: Total Issues grouped by status

Status	Issues	%
Quality Check passed	86	38%
Duplicate	71	31%
Out of scope	67	30%
Quality Check Failed	3	1%

The following diagram reports the labels distribution among the issues in the database.

Figure 73: Frequency of labels assigned to database entries

Label	Issues	%
Satisfaction	57	12,9%
Sunlight	43	9,8%
Operator	42	9,5%
Productivity	34	7,7%
Organisation	32	7,3%
Usability	28	6,3%
Communication	28	6,3%
Training	26	5,9%
Safety	25	5,7%
Teamwork	22	5,0%

Motivation	21	4,8%
Problem to solve	18	4,1%
CERTH-CPERI	16	3,6%
Gamification	10	2,3%
Trainee	9	2,0%
Process Supervisor	8	1,8%
Foreman	8	1,8%
WP4	3	0,7%
Further Education	3	0,7%
Mechanical Operator	2	0,5%
COMAU	2	0,5%
Privacy	1	0,2%
Maintenance	1	0,2%
Hiring	1	0,2%
Ergonomy	1	0,2%

The following diagram shows the issues in the database shown by Creator.

Figure 74: Total Issues per Creator

Creator	Project Partner	Issues	%
Marc Jentsch	FIT	95	41%
Pietro Cultrona	COMAU	60	26%
Sarah Suleri	FIT	30	13%
Svetlana Matiouk	FIT	12	5%
Erion Elmasllari	FIT	11	4%
Stelios Krinidis	CERTH/ITI	8	3%
Chrysovalantou Ziogou	CERTH/CPERI	7	3%
Stylianos Zikos	CERTH/ITI	2	0%
Symeon Parcharidis	SUNLIGHT	1	0%
Hussein Khaleel	ISMB	1	0%

The following Chart shows the Requirements organized by Type:

Figure 75: Total Requirements grouped by type

Typology	Issues	%
Functional	80	35,2%
Irrelevant	47	20,7%
None	24	10,6%
Non-Functional	23	10,1%
Non-Functional-usability	21	9,3%
Non-Functional-operational	18	7,9%
Non-Functional-look and feel	5	2,2%
Non-Functional-performance	2	0,9%
Constraint-requirement constraint	2	0,9%
Project Issue-open issue	1	0,4%
Non-Functional-maintainability	1	0,4%
Constraint	1	0,4%

SATISFACTORY

Constraint-purpose	1	0,4%
Constraint-end-users	1	0,4%

6. CONCLUSIONS

The present document is the third version of the deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020), reporting the results of the activities carried out by WP1, that will manage and undertake the work in carrying out the iterative engineering of requirements, which special focuses on the engineering process of initial requirements and reengineering after the end of each iteration cycle.

Moreover this WorkPackage maintains a continuous discovery and analysis of user centric requirements, needs and prospects, to be used in the design, development, implementation and validation of the SatisFactory platform and services.

The main achievements reported in this document are the formalisation of the requirements to be addressed in the prototype applications for the three end-users test-beds: discrete manufacturing in automotive (to which maintenance scenario has been added), discrete manufacturing for batteries and continuous process in chemical applications. Specifically, the goal of this document is to define a list of requirements exploiting the "Volere" approach, that will be continuously updated and refined through an iterative process that will lead to the production of a total of three releases of this deliverable, respectively in Project Months M4, M14 and M26.

In particular, it is worth to highlight that the collection of requirements, performed through more than forty (40) face-to-face interviews of end-user employees, followed by brainstorming sessions among technology partners, provided in the first iteration eighty-three (83) initial requirements. While in the second iteration (M16) the identified requirements become 227. In particular, 89 requirements are in the status of "Quality Check passed", while 66 have been identified "Out of Scope" and 69 as "Duplicated" after filtering, homogenization and merging them.

These topics will be the main areas of improvement that the SatisFactory project considered during development phases performed in the technical WorkPackages and validated through an iterative process, and that will be the basis for improvement and future industrial spreading of SatisFactory solutions. The final update of this document has been performed in M26, during its third iteration.

REFERENCES

EFFRA, Factories Of the Future - Multi-annual roadmap for the contractual PPP under Horizon 2020, European Union, 2013

INDUSTRIE 4.0, <http://www.bmbf.de/>, <http://www.hightech-strategie.de/>

SMLC, Smart Manufacturing Leadership Coalition, <https://smartmanufacturingcoalition.org/>

Chin, G., M.B. Rosson, and J.M. Carroll. Participatory analysis: shared development of requirements from scenarios. in SIGCHI conference on Human factors in computing systems. 1997.

Easterbrook, S., Negotiation and the Role of the Requirements Specification. Appears in P. Quintas (ed.) Social Dimensions of Systems Engineering: People, processes, policies and software development, 1993: p. 144-164.

Glinz, M., Improving the Quality of Requirements with Scenarios, in Proceeding of the Second World Conference on Requirements Engineering. 2000: Schaumburg. p. 254-271.

Gomaa, H. and D.B.H. Scott. Prototyping as a tool in the specification of user requirements. in Proceedings of the 5th international conference on Software engineering. 1981. San Diego, California, United States.

Healthy Workplace - Manage Stress, https://www.healthy-workplaces.eu/en?set_language=en

Holbrook H., I., A scenario-based methodology for conducting requirements elicitation SIGSOFT Softw. Eng. Notes 1990 15 (1): p. 95-104

ISO, ISO 9241-210:2010 Ergonomics of human-system interaction – Part 210: Human-centred design for interactive systems. International Organization for Standardization, 2010.

Jarke, M. and K. Pohl, Requirements engineering in 2001: (virtually) managing a changing reality. IEEE Software Engineering, 1994. 9(6).

MoSCoW Method. 2015; Wikipedia, http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MoSCoW_method

OSHA, Safety Devices. 2003; <https://www.osha.gov/Publications/osha3151.html>

Penna, G.D., et al., An XML Definition Language to Support Scenario-Based Requirements Engineering. International Journal of Software Engineering and Knowledge Engineering, 2003. 13(3): p. 237-256.

Ramesh, B. and M. Jarke, Toward Reference Models for Requirements Traceability. IEEE Trans. Softw. Eng., 2001. 27(1): p. 58-93.

Robertson, J. and Robertson, S.; Requirements-Led Project Management. 2004: Addison-Wesley.

Robertson, J. and Robertson, S.; Mastering the Requirements Process. 1999: Addison-Wesley.

Robertson, J. and Robertson, S.; Volere Requirements Specification Template. 2010.

Stufflebeam, W., A.I. Antón, and T.A. Alspaugh. SMaRT – Scenario Management and Requirements Tool. in 11th IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference. 2003.

Sutcliffe, A.G., W.-C. Chang, and R. Neville, Evolutionary Requirements Analysis, in 11th IEEE Requirements Engineering Conference. 2003.

Sutcliffe, A.G. Scenario-based Requirements Engineering. in 11th IEEE International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE'03). 2003.

Zimmerman, J., Stolterman, E., and Forlizzi, J. An Analysis and Critique of Research Through Design: Towards a Formalization of a Research Approach. In Proceedings of the 8th ACM Conference on Designing Interactive Systems, 2010: ACM Press, p. 310–319.

ANNEX 1 – INTERVIEW NOTES AND TEMPLATE

Notes & guidelines for conducting the interviews

General Tips:

- Project presentation
- Data will remain confidential
- Only aggregated data will be shown at the end
- Create a friendly atmosphere: make small talk
- Distance yourself from the enterprise and make clear that the answers will be confidential, best: Hire someone external to do this. Psychology/Sociology students will be fine
- This interview should feel like two friends in a coffee bar
- Use these questions for you, to steer the conversation
- Change them as you see fit for the situation
- Set a hierarchy of questions in your mind and be ready to leave out non-essential questions in favour of important ones
- Remember that we are trying to improve happiness and satisfaction
- Questions allowed: Who, What, Why, What for, How, When

Section 1 –Company general information

1. What is the company's core business? [Industry sector]
2. Total revenues in 2014? [MEuro]
3. Number of Employees at the end of 2014? [Number]

Section 2 – Stakeholder general information

1. Contact information? [person name, age, phone, email]
2. Which is your education degree? [Vocational, BS, MS]
3. What is your actual role in the company? [Job title]
4. Years of experience in the actual role? [Number]
5. Which are your main areas of expertise? [3-5 areas]
6. How did you come to do this job? [Social, Newspapers, Networking]
7. What is best & worst about working in this field/job?
8. Would you recommend your son/daughter/friend to do the same job? [Y/N, Why?]

Section 3 – Activities/Work description

1. Which are your/your workers' "typical working day" activities?
2. Can you describe your workplace?
3. What tools do you use for your work? [Nr, type]
4. How do you do your work, what is involved in the process?
5. Do you use any specific safety device? [Safety shoes, gloves, glasses, helmet]
6. How is your working time organized? How much flexibility do you have with it?
 - a. How do you feel about that?
7. What procedures are there to validate timing and quality of the work performed?

8. What extraordinary activities are there in your working day?
 - a. What happens rarely, but is problematic or disturbing to you?
9. Do you perform your daily activities individually or in collaboration with others?
 - a. How do you collaborate with them?

Section 4 – Employees turnover

1. How many years do you think people stay in the company on average?
2. How much time does it take to fill a job opening?
3. Most common reasons for people going away?
4. Most common reason for the length it takes to fill an opening?
5. What has been tried to increase satisfaction/lower turnover? What were the results?

Section 5 – Training received

1. What training did you get for this work?
 - a. How long did the training period last?
 - b. How many years ago it was performed?
 - c. How would you train someone to do your job? Or, how would you have wished to be trained?

Section 6 – Procedures and guidelines applied (plus IT support)

1. In your working activities what specific procedures do you follow? What is good and what is bad about them?
2. What documents are there to guide you in these procedures, or what documents are needed as part of these procedures?
3. What electronic devices do you use in these procedures? [Computers, Tablet, HMI, ...]
4. How are the procedures or work orders told to you?

Section 7 – Working scenario improvement

1. What bothers you most about your work? How would you improve it?
2. Do you think that the actual procedures and guidelines could be improved?
3. Do you think that the actual IT support to access the existing procedures should be improved? (e.g. introducing terminals, touchscreens, mobile devices....)
4. Do you feel the need of some additional training?
5. In the complex, which is your degree of satisfaction of the actual workplace?

Section 8 – Other suggestions

1. Do you have any other suggestion?

ANNEX 2 – REQUIREMENTS TEMPLATE (VOLERE)

Requirement No.:	Requirement Type:	Use Cases:
Description:		
Rationale:		
Source:		
Fit Criterion:		
Customer Satisfaction Rating:	Customer Dissatisfaction Rating:	
Dependencies:	Conflicts:	
History:	Supporting Materials:	

ANNEX 3 – LEGISLATION REVIEW

EUROPEAN LEGISLATION

The EU has established the legal framework which is categorised below.

PERSONAL DATA

- **Protection of personal data**

The protection of personal data is ensured by Directive 95/46/EC on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. The Directive applies to the processing of individuals' personal data by other individuals, businesses, public authorities, etc. This concerns the processing of data wholly or partly by automatic means and the processing of data that form part of a filing system.

The aim of the Directive is to protect the fundamental rights and freedoms of individuals, in particular their right to privacy with respect to the processing of personal data. Under the Directive, data must be collected fairly and lawfully, which means collection for specified and legitimate purposes. Furthermore, the data must be accurate and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which it was collected. The Directive forbids the keeping of the data for longer than necessary. The organisation collecting the data is under the obligation to ensure the confidentiality and security of their processing. The processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs and trade-union membership is forbidden, as is the processing of data concerning health or sex life. This does however not apply when the person involved has given his or her explicit consent or when the processing is necessary for employment law purposes, in which case adequate safeguards will need to be provided. The person on whom data is being collected must be informed of the identity of the organisation collecting that data and of its reason for doing so. The Directive also gives individuals the right to access data held on them except in certain cases such as police and HM Revenue & Customs records. In addition, the Directive provides for the right to have the data corrected and the right to object to certain types of data being processed in some instances.

The organisation collecting and processing the data is under the obligation to notify an independent supervisory body before carrying out wholly or partly automatic data processing operations. Those in business in the EU therefore have to register and ensure that they have procedures in place to give individuals copies of the data held on them. Those who suffer damage because of unlawful processing have a right to sue for damages. Individuals are also given the right to object to their data being held for direct marketing purposes.

INFORMATION AND CONSULTATION OF EMPLOYEES

- **Informing and consulting employees**

Directive 2002/14/EC establishes a general framework for informing and consulting employees in the European Community. The purpose of this Directive is to establish a general framework setting out minimum requirements for employees' rights and for consultation of employees in undertakings or establishments across the EU. The scope of the Directive is restricted to undertakings with minimum 50 employees or establishments employing at least 20 employees. The Directive outlines broad guidelines and practical arrangements that are to be defined and implemented in accordance with national law and industrial relations practices in the individual Member States.

Under the Directive, employers have to disclose any information regarding the recent and probable development of the organisation's activities and economic situation. Employees also have to be kept informed of the situation of employment within the undertaking or establishment and of any envisaged measures, in particular when there is a threat to employment. Finally, decisions likely to lead to substantial changes in the work organisation or contractual relations have to be made known to employees. The information has to be given at such a time, in such a fashion and with such content as is appropriate to enable employees' representatives to carry out an adequate study and, where necessary, prepare for consultation. Consultation has to be organised at the appropriate time at the relevant level of management and representation, and in such a way that enables employees' representatives to meet the employer and obtain a response. The Directive does not cover confidential information.

ANTI-DISCRIMINATION

- **Workplace discrimination**

Directive 2000/78/EC establishes a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation, which forbids discrimination based on religion, belief, disability, age and sexual orientation.

- **Racial and ethnic discrimination**

The general principle of anti-discrimination is safeguarded at the EU level by Directive 2000/43/EC implementing the principle of equal treatment between persons irrespective of racial or ethnic origin. The Directive covers areas such as education, social protection (social security and healthcare), social advantages and access to and supply of goods and services and goes beyond access to employment and self-employment (covered by Directive 2000/78/EC outlined above).

- **Equal treatment of men and women in the workplace**

Equality between men and women in the workplace is guaranteed by three pieces of EU legislation.

- **The Equal Pay Directive**

Directive 75/117/EC on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to the application of the principle of equal pay for men and women.

- **The Equal Treatment Directive**

Directive 76/207/EC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and working conditions. (Directive 2002/73/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 September 2002 amending Council Directive

76/207/EEC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women as regards access to employment, vocational training and promotion, and working conditions, Directive 2006/54/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 July 2006 on the implementation of the principle of equal opportunities and equal treatment of men and women in matters of employment and occupation).

- **The Equal Social Security Directive**

Directive 86/378/EEC on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment for men and women in occupational social security schemes.

GREEK LEGISLATION

The Greek legislation is in accordance to the EU legislation. In Greece, the law N. 2472/1997 (and amendments N. 3471/2006, N. 3783/2009, N. 3917/2011, N. 4070/2012 and N. 4139/2013), define the framework for the protection of personal data. The individuals, in relation to data collection, have the rights to: information, access, objection, interim judicial protection. Personal data is any piece information referring to the "data subject", the individual. "Data Subject" is the natural person to whom the data refer and whose identity is known or can be ascertained, that can be determined directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identification number or to one or more factors specific to his or her physiological, mental, economic, cultural, political or social substance.

According to article 7A of N. 2472/1997 the monitoring party is exempted from the notification requirement in some cases, one of which is: "When the processing is done by unions, companies, firms, associations and political parties and relates to data of their members or their companies if they have given their consent and data is not transmitted or communicated to third parties". It is noted that the monitoring is part of SatisFactory project and that the companies providing the pilot plants are partners in the project. It would be preferable that the employees participating in the pilot trial give their consent.

The Hellenic Data Protection Authority issues Directives on related matters. The most relative to our project are:

Directive 115/2001 was issued for the interpretation of law N. 2472/1997 and N. 2774/99. This Directive explicitly notes examples of recruitment procedures, in the attempt to interpret the legislation. It is stated that the personal data of the employees must be collected and processed for precisely defined purposes. Under the N. 2472/1997 law, the employer is obliged to inform the workers, and this suggests that the purposes of the processing should be known in advance to employees and understood by them.

Personal data collected in connection with technical or organizational measures to ensure the correct and safe system operation cannot be used to control the behaviour of employees, unless it is associated with the operation of these systems.

Modern methods of personnel selection include examinations, tests or procedures for the assessment of qualifications, skills and abilities of the candidate. These examinations and analysis may reveal or make reference to aspects of personality, related beliefs, traditions and spiritual or mental health / condition of a person. Due to the nature of the data, their collection is legally permissible only with the written consent of the candidate, and after informing him/her about the method, criteria, objectives and (potential) recipients of the analysis and results. The applicant

should be informed of the results and the data should be erased or destroyed as soon they fulfil the purpose of collection, unless the applicant specifically requests the preservation of the data.

Regarding personal data concerning the health of the worker or candidate must be collected directly and only by the workers or candidates and only as long as it is absolutely necessary for the evaluation of the suitability of the employee or candidate for a specific position or job. The collection of personal data using control methods and monitoring of workers must be limited to the data that are directly related to the employment and should not be extended to the personal behaviour, characteristics or personal internal and external contacts of the workers. Continuous control should only occur if it is justified by the nature and conditions of work and if it is necessary to protect the health and safety of workers and the safety of workplaces.

Directive 1/2005 on the secure destruction of personal data, after the time needed after the period required to carry out the purpose that required processing of the data. It is noted that this Directive shall not apply in the case that the data is rendered anonymous by the controller after the end of the treatment period.

Moreover, the Greek Constitution (1975/1986/2001) recognises the principle of privacy, which in fact is a combination of the protection of human dignity, liberty, the confidentiality of communications and the imposition of restrictions on state and private economic activity. This principle implies the right of everyone to protect his/her dignity, his/her freedom, the space in which he/she is moving and his/her personal activities, from any carrier and any process.

ITALIAN LEGISLATION

The Italian legislation is in general accordance with EU legislation. The main reference code is Data Protection Code - Legislative Decree no. 196/2003.

Introduction

Italy's consolidated data protection code came into force on 1 January 2004. The Code brings together all the various laws, codes and regulations relating to data protection since 1996. In particular, it supersedes the Data Protection Act 1996 (no. 675/1996), which had come into effect in May 1997.

There are three key guiding principles behind the code, which are outlined in section 2:

1. Simplification
2. Harmonization
3. Effectiveness

The code is divided into three parts. The first part sets out the general data protection principles that apply to all organizations. Part two of the code provides additional measures that will need to be undertaken by organizations in certain areas, for example, healthcare, telecommunications, banking and finance, or human resources. Part three relates to sanctions and remedies. It is expected that the second part of the code will be developed further through the introduction of sectorial codes of practice.

Scope of the Italian data protection code - The code applies to all processing within the State and its territories. It will also affect outside organizations that make use of equipment located within Italy, which could include e.g. PCs and other computer-based systems (see Section 5 of the Code). If an organization outside the EU is processing data on Italian territory, it must appoint a representative in Italy for the application of Italian rules (this will be necessary for notifying with the “Garante”, if notification is due, and providing data subjects with information notices).

Main Features of the Data Protection Code

Notification - One of the key targets for simplification was the notification process, which was made more straightforward compared to the 1996 Act in line with the EU Data Protection Directive - which allows the notification process to be simplified in cases where data processing does not adversely affect the rights and freedoms of data subjects (see Article 18(2) of the directive). Under the Italian code, organizations are only required to notify the “Garante” when processing higher-risk categories of data. These include, in particular, genetic and biometric data, data processed for the purpose of analyzing or profiling individuals, and credit-related information (see Section 37 of the code for additional details). This approach is also aimed at making the process more transparent and understandable for individuals.

Data minimization - Section 3 of the code introduces the element of data minimization into Italian data protection. The code encourages organizations to make use of non-personal data whenever possible.

Data subjects' rights/Decision taking - The code aims to strengthen individuals' data protection rights, allowing them to exercise their rights and instigate proceedings more easily. In an effort to simplify the complaints process, the “Garante” has published a complaints form on its website. The “Garante” can also order businesses to abide by compliance requirements set out in its decisions. When responding to investigations, businesses now have 15 days to comply, compared to the previous 5-day timeframe. The turnaround for dealing with complaints has been raised to 60 days (previously it was 30 days); this period was found to be suitable in order for the “Garante” to work effectively and the parties to prepare their pleadings appropriately.

International Data Transfers - The data protection Code has incorporated and, to some extent, updated the previous rules on data transfers (data transfers are addressed in Sections 42-45 of the Code). Whereas previously businesses had to notify the “Garante” of their intention to transfer data outside the EU, under the new system companies will only have to provide notification in cases in which the transfer of data could prejudice data subjects' rights (see the Notification section). Additionally, the new system does not require organizations to resubmit notifications each year. The rules for legitimizing transfers to non-EU countries can be found in Section 43 of the Code and include consent, meeting contractual obligations, public interest requirements, safeguarding life/health, investigations by defense counsel, use of publicly available data, processing for statistical/historical purposes. Additional provisions for legitimizing transfers are laid out in Section 44 of the Code and include transfers to countries deemed adequate by the European Commission,

the adoption of contractual safeguards, and the use of binding corporate rules. Data subjects are entitled to lodge claims in Italy for non-compliance with the said contractual/corporate safeguards.

Main Features in Respect of Specific Processing Operations

Human Resources Data - The code has fully implemented Article 8 (b) of the EU directive which applies to the processing of data. Organizations processing sensitive data that wish to find an alternative to the somewhat unreliable issues of employee consent, can look at the exemptions laid out in Section 26 of the code. For example, Section 26 (4d) allows the processing of sensitive data without consent if necessary to meet obligations under employment law.

Health data - Processing is allowed with the data subject's consent (which must be provided in writing) and the Garante's authorisation if the data controller is a private body. As for public bodies, processing is allowed if it is provided for in laws/regulations; however, the latter must set out the specific processing operations and purposes in detail, otherwise the relevant public bodies must specify them via ad-hoc regulatory instruments. The data subject's consent is not required, in principle, whilst the Garante's authorisation is necessary except for the processing by health care professionals that is indispensable with a view to the data subject's health and/or bodily integrity. The Garante's authorisation has been granted in the form of an instrument applying to several entities and/or processing operations, i.e. as a "General Authorization for the Processing of Sensitive Data" by various categories of data controller (see Legislation section). It should be recalled that specific provisions are laid down in the DP Code to regulate the processing of medical data in the health care sector (Sections 75-94). In particular, health care professionals and public health care bodies may process medical data (the Code refers to "data suitable for disclosing health") with the data subject's consent and without the Garante's authorization if the processing concerns data and operations that are indispensable with a view to the data subject's health and/or bodily integrity; conversely, they may process medical data without the data subject's consent but with the Garante's authorization if the processing is indispensable to safeguard public health.

Electronic Communications Data - The Code has implemented the provisions contained in the E-Communications privacy directive 2002/58/EC as well as in the data retention directive (2006/24/EC) (see Title 10, Part 2 of the Code). One of the main principles is on electronic marketing which requires organizations to obtain prior consent before sending electronic marketing to consumers (see Section 130). This applies to all forms of e-marketing, including e-mail, fax, SMS/MMS etc.. Specific provisions were added to regulate telemarketing. There is also a ban on sending e-marketing from anonymous addresses - this is a breach of the data protection code as the data controller has withheld its identity. As for data retention, communications service providers (CSPs) are permitted to retain traffic data for only a six-month period in order to deal with disputes over billing and subscriber services (section 123(2)). CSPs are also required to retain traffic data for longer in connection with law enforcement purposes; the retention periods are currently set at twenty-four months (telephone traffic data) and twelve months (electronic communications traffic data), irrespective of the given offence at issue (in pursuance of directive 2006/24/EC) (see section 132). Following ratification of Council of Europe's Cybercrime Convention (via Act no. 48/2008,

which amended Section 132 of the DP Code), police authorities were enabled, under specific circumstances, to order IT and/or Internet service providers and operators to retain and protect Internet traffic data - except for contents data- for no longer than ninety days, in order to carry out pre-trial investigations or else with a view to the detection and suppression of specific offences. The order issued by police authorities must be notified to and validated by the competent public prosecutor.

Main Features as to Compliance and Enforcement

Complaints - Data subjects can settle disputes either through the courts or by lodging a complaint with the Garante in case they have been prevented from exercising access, erasure, rectification, updating rights (as per Section 7 of the code). Organisations have 30 15 days to respond and can appeal to the Garante for more time. The Garante will then have 60 days to consider the request (see above "Data Subjects' Rights/Decision Taking").

Inspections - The Garante's inspection powers are laid out in Section 158 of the code. When investigating organizations, the Garante can request information and documents, although these requests are not legally binding. However, if there is no cooperation, and the organizations refuses access to its systems, the Garante can apply for a judicial order to carry out an investigation.

When carrying out formal inspections, the Garante can demand copies of manual records and databases, which may be passed onto the judicial authorities. A report of the outcome is then published.

CONCLUSION

Consequently, for the implementation of T1.1 Satisfactory, contacting workers and stakeholders through questionnaires or interviews does not oppose to current legislation, as long as we keep them informed on the type of data collected, processed and stored, on the scope of the data collection and as long as we have their consent (for the case of collection of personal data).

REFERENCES

1. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/> accessed February 2015
2. http://www.dpa.gr/portal/page?_pageid=33,15145&_dad=portal&_schema=PORTAL accessed February 2015
3. Directive 95/46/EC
4. Directive 2002/14/EC
5. Directive 2000/78/EC
6. Directive 2000/43/EC
7. Directive 75/117/EC
8. Directive 76/207/EC

9. Directive 2002/73/EC
10. Directive 2006/54/EC
11. Directive 86/378/EEC
12. N. 2472/1997 (and amendments N. 3471/2006, N. 3783/2009, N. 3917/2011, N. 4070/2012 and N. 4139/2013)
13. Greek Constitution
14. Hellenic Data Protection Authority Directive 1/2005
15. Hellenic Data Protection Authority Directive 115/2001
16. Guidance 2001/29/EC
17. <http://www.een-ireland.ie/eei/assets/documents/uploaded/general/EU%20Labour%20law.pdf> accessed February 2015
18. <http://www.londonchamber.co.uk/DocImages/1154.pdf> accessed February 2015 Mr. Vassilis Papachristos, Director - Northern Greece Branch at ICAP, Personal communication February 2015

ANNEX 4 – WORKPLACES ERGONOMICS

GENERAL ASPECTS

In order to achieve a full transformation of factories into attractive workplaces, designing factories as places that provide pleasant working experience, it is necessary to take into consideration also the aspects related to the interaction between workers and machines (safety and ergonomics).

Ergonomics, according to International Ergonomics Association, is “the scientific discipline concerned with the understanding of interactions among humans and other elements of a system, and the profession that applies theory, principles, data and methods to design in order to optimize human well-being and overall system performance”.

We usually refer to ergonomics meaning all actions taken to guarantee a satisfactory working condition under general constraints of health and safety regulations.

The European Community directives on safety at work and their national implementations have given a new and deeper impulse to the study of working places more and more satisfying for the workers. We can say that the directives have given a very strong impulse to develop harmonized standards and draft standards on the issues of ergonomics. The comfort in work environment is now gaining increasing importance under the pressure of the market, and there is therefore a higher attention of the European legislation for this issue.

However, it must be noted that the quantity and breadth of these standards are not even remotely comparable with standards developed in other fields, such as that of the machine safety. While the ergonomics science is now widespread (at least in all industrially developed countries), with many years of practice, we have to remark that from the point of view of practical solutions, consolidated applications are still missing.

The social policy of European Community states, but also from other continents (North America), is now increasingly appreciating the benefits deriving from a new approach towards working conditions as an important enabling factor to enhance overall profitability. Very often, however, a traditional approach tends to consider ergonomics as an additional cost for machinery and equipment, neglecting thus the crucial aspect that comfortable workplaces bring many and important benefits to the factory productivity (from economic as well as from social point of view). Anyway, at least in the first implementation phases, additional expenses and investments are undeniably needed to ensure a safe and comfortable working environment.

Companies operating in a mass production paradigm must know the level of performance of the worker and strive to improve working efficiency: this is especially true where the employee are delegated tasks more and more complex, due to the greater flexibility of man if compared with machines (even automatic). If we consider a typical automotive scenario, in usual practice assembly lines composed by a large number of manual stations show significant advantages in terms of production flexibility improvements, but there is a typical drawback in terms of production efficiency of the system when the cycle time of manual stations becomes very low. This may be very well highlighted through a virtual discrete event simulation. The reason of production worsening lies in the fact that the workers employed in a specific manual workstations cannot keep the cycle

theoretically assigned to them during the shift, if this cycle has not been previously calculated and thoroughly determined with the scientific and technical tools developed by ergonomic science. This is a first proof that ergonomics compliance costs may be highly compensated for by related productive benefits.

We can say that the calculation of the cycle time for manual or semiautomatic workstations are not possible without a careful ergonomic analysis, which will have to verify the correctness of the cycle time calculated by the formal tools of Work Analysis.

Fig. 1 - Health risk associated with postures

Figure 2: A model of the health risks associated with postures and movements

Fig. 2 - Dimensions for human-machinery interaction

The combined use of Work Analysis and Ergonomic Load can provide very useful information to verify the theoretical productivity of an assembly plant and thus its overall actual performance. The calculation of cycle time (starting from the analysis of micro-movements related to the task to be performed), verified through ergonomic and safety analysis, in conjunction with the discrete event simulation of production process, will enable a reasonable confidence of overall system performance. Furthermore, with the study of Life Cycle Cost, it will be possible to compare different options for systems layout, for manual/automatic stations as well as mixed solutions.

The careful ergonomic study of the working stations, combined with the system simulation, may suggest improvements related to different configurations and balance of the same stations. The analysis may give indications on the possibility to add or remove operations at a given station to increase or reduce the cycle time (therefore affecting the ergonomic load), keeping under control the ultimate goal of the overall productivity of the line, through the measurement of its global performance.

In general, ergonomic science was conceived starting from the concept that the human worker comes first, and then the environment and working equipment is built around him.

RULA Employee Assessment Worksheet

Complete this worksheet following the step-by-step procedure below. Keep a copy in the employee's personnel folder for future reference.

A. Arm & Wrist Analysis

Step 1: Locate Upper Arm Position

Step 2: Locate Lower Arm Position

Step 3: Locate Wrist Position

Step 4: Wrist Twist

Step 5: Look-up Posture Score in Table A

Step 6: Add Muscle Use Score

Step 7: Add Force/load Score

Step 8: Find Row in Table C

SCORES

Table A

Table B

Table C

B. Neck, Trunk & Leg Analysis

Step 9: Locate Neck Position

Step 10: Locate Trunk Position

Step 11: Legs

Step 12: Look-up Posture Score in Table B

Step 13: Add Muscle Use Score

Step 14: Add Force/load Score

Step 15: Find Column in Table C

Subject: _____ Date: ____/____/____
 Company: _____ Department: _____ Scorer: ____/____/____

FINAL SCORE: 1 or 2 = Acceptable; 3 or 4 investigate further; 5 or 6 investigate further and change soon; 7 investigate and change immediately

Source: McAtamney, L. & Corlett, E.N. (1993) RULA: a survey method for the investigation of work-related upper limb disorders, Applied Ergonomics, 24(2) 91-99.
 © Professor Alan Hedge, Cornell University, Feb. 2001

Fig. 3 - Example of employees ergonomics assessment table

This concept, expressed as a formal need and objective, should gradually evolve from the stage of theoretical analysis to a wide practical implementation, considering all factors possibly influencing the technical solutions to be devised.

Table 1: Recommended mass constant (M_c) taking into consideration the intended user populations

Field of application	M_c kg	Percentage of population group				
		F&M	F	M		
Domestic use	5	Data not available			Children and the elderly General domestic population	Total population
	10	99	99	99		
Professional use	15	95	90	99	General working population, including the young and old Adult working population	General working population
	25	85	70	90		
	30	Data not available			Specialized working population	Specialized working population under special circumstances
	35	Data not available				
40	Data not available					

F: Female M: Male
 NOTE: Special circumstances
 While every effort should be made to avoid manual handling activities or reduce the risks to the lowest possible levels, there may be exceptional circumstances where the recommended mass constant may exceed 25 kg (e.g. where technological developments or interventions are not sufficiently advanced). In these exceptional circumstances, special consideration must be given to the education and training of the individual (e.g. specialized knowledge concerning risk identification and risk reduction), the working conditions which prevail and the capabilities of the individual.

Fig. 4 - Examples of measurement tables for work loads

A wide implementation of ergonomics in industrial environment requires nevertheless a great work in systematically designing specific feasible solutions for any technical scenario, thus allowing to embed ergonomic compliance during design phase without additional effort.

Simulation tools play a big role in implementing ergonomics.

Fig. 5 - Example of s/w simulation of working station

The main problem of simulation is that very often ergonomic standards (e.g. for effort limits and anthropometric measurements) are different between Europe and other states like US. This problem is present at any level in legislation.

European legislation sometimes refers, in the regulations for the practical implementation of laws, to rules issued by US authorities, even when similar issues have been dealt with by European harmonized standards. On the other hand individual states, but also local governments, normally issue their own regulations, which finally become a legal constraint to be respected by manufacturers and end-users of machinery.

A strong need for harmonization is required, to avoid having different laws and regulation in different states in the same context, with the consequent additional effort for machinery producer. The European Union is undeniably making a big effort in issuing complete and extensive ergonomic norms, even if for some issues there is still the need to refer to US standards, while for others no standards are available as yet.

RELEVANT STANDARDS IN ERGONOMICS AND FIELDS OF APPLICATION

The concept of ergonomics is closely connected with safety: we can hardly speak of ergonomics if we do not address the issues of security and vice versa. The two aspects of safety and ergonomics are complementary: a machine must be safe, but must also be manageable by workers in all operating conditions, and therefore it must also be ergonomic.

It is not conceivable to have a safe machine, but unmanageable by the worker in production or maintenance phase: sooner or later, the workers would be trying to bypass safety equipment to fully operate the machinery.

We can therefore say that a theoretically safe machine, which is not also ergonomic, will not be really safe, as it will inherently lead to non-safe behaviour by the human operator. The contrary is not true, since ergonomics takes formally into account all aspects of human-machine interaction, and thus the safety requirements as well. Thus, an ergonomic machine will be also safe by definition.

Table 1

	Static posture	Movement	
		low frequency (< 2/minute)	high frequency (≥ 2 /minute)
I*	acceptable	ACCEPTABLE	acceptable
II	conditionally acceptable (step 2A)	acceptable	not acceptable
III	not acceptable	conditionally acceptable (step 2C)	not acceptable
IV	conditionally acceptable (step 2B)	conditionally acceptable (step 2C)	not acceptable

Figure 3: Trunk bending forward/backward • It is recommended to strive for working postures with an upright trunk.

Fig. 6 - Examples of table for workers right posture

If we consider the application area of manufacturing systems, we have many applicable standards referring in general to safety/ergonomics.

Fig. 7 - Example of weight lifting posture

Focusing mainly on European/USA areas, we can list the following norms as highly relevant to the design of manufacturing plants and machinery:

- EN 547-1 "Safety of machinery. Human body measurements. Principles for determining the dimensions required for openings for whole body access into machinery"
- EN 547-2 "Safety of machinery. Human body measurements. Principles for determining the dimensions required for access openings"
- EN 547-3 "Safety of machinery. Human body measurements. Anthropometric data"
- EN 1005-1 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 1: Terms and definitions"
- EN 1005-2 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 2: Manual handling of machinery and component parts of machinery"

- EN 1005-3 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 3: Recommended force limits for machinery operations"
- EN 1005-4 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 4: Evaluation of working postures and movements in relation to machinery"
- EN 1005-5 "Safety of machinery. Human physical performance. Part 5: Risk assessment for repetitive handling at high frequency"
- ISO 11228-1 "Ergonomics. Manual handling. Part 1: Lifting and carrying"
- ISO 11228-2 "Ergonomics. Manual handling. Part 2: Pushing and pulling"
- ISO 11228-3 "Ergonomics. Manual handling. Part 3: Handling of low loads at high frequency"
- ISO EN 14738 "Safety of machinery. Anthropometric requirements for the design of workstations at machinery"
- EN 614-1 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomic design principles. Terminology and general principles"
- EN 614-2 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomic design principles. Part 2: Interactions between the design of machinery and work tasks"
- ISO EN 894-1 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomics requirements for the design of displays and control actuators. General principles for human interactions with displays and control actuators"
- ISO EN 894-2 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomics requirements for the design of displays and control actuators. Displays"
- ISO EN 894-3 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomics requirements for the design of displays and control actuators. Control actuators"
- ISO EN 894-4 "Safety of machinery. Ergonomics requirements for the design of displays and control actuators. Location and arrangement of displays and control actuators"
- ISO EN 7250-1 "Basic human body measurements for technological design. Part 1: Body measurement definitions and landmarks"
- ISO EN 7250-2 "Basic human body measurements for technological design. Part 2: Statistical summaries of body measurements from national populations"

Fig. 8 - Examples of field of application of standards

Other relevant guidelines for enhancing ergonomics in factories may be found under OHSAS 18001 (“OHSAS: Occupation Health and Safety Assessment Series”), a specification for safety management systems inside organizations.

Fig. 9 - OHS Management System

Another important source of information is represented by US NIOSH (National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health) standards.

Fig. 10 - example of job stress model bu NIOSH

Each norm deals with specific subjects referred to the interaction between the human worker and the machinery, establishing the average values to be taken as a reference in designing machines.

ANNEX 5 – INFORMED CONSENT FOR INTERVIEWS

[PILOT SITE]

(COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH)

Project Title: *SatisFactory - A collaborative and augmented-enabled ecosystem for increasing satisfaction and working experience in smart factory environments*

GENERAL DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT AND PURPOSE OF USE (BACKGROUND)

SatisFactory aims to enhance and enrich the manufacturing working environment towards attractive factories of the future that encompass key enabling technologies such as augmented reality, wearable and ubiquitous computing as well as and customised social communication platforms coupled with experience design and gamification techniques for the efficient transfer of knowledge and experience among employees.

The ultimate goal is to develop and deploy emerging knowledge-driven training techniques (gamification aware) and wearable devices (AR-enabled Glasses) for the enhancement of innovation, productivity and scheduling of work in the production line while enriching its flexibility through the support of team interactions in the shop floor which consequently will add to the work-related satisfaction. Special attention in the deployment of cutting-edge incentives (wearable computing, gamified working experience) will be given towards further increase of attractiveness to the younger generation.

Project Objectives and Expected Results

The project foresees to achieve its main goals through multi-disciplinary technologies stemming from the deployment of a “plug-and-share” multi-sensorial framework for collecting effectively tacit knowledge generated in the factory environment, the delivery of a semantically enriched knowledge modelling framework (based on envisioned Common Information Data Exchange Model - CIDEM) for supporting on job education of workers as well as for incident management and proactive maintenance, whereas it will provide the capability to automatically verify the correctness of actions performed by the operators in the field, which accommodated by novel head-mounted displays (next generation AR Glasses provided by GlassUp partner). In parallel, the focus on user experience and gamification will ensure optimal balance between workers performance and satisfaction.

The specific technical project objectives and the corresponding expected results are summarised as follows:

Objective 1: Context-aware control and re-adaptation of shop floor production facilities for increased productivity and flexibility in use of shop floor resources.

SatisFactory will introduce a novel multi-sensorial framework to collect multi-modal data from the shop floor related to thermal and optical data of production outputs, workplace occupancy data, numeric measurements such as temperature, acceleration, vibration, and distension, which will be aggregated and processed, creating a semantically enhanced base of knowledge.

Objective 2: Improvement of attractiveness and productivity through collaboration, social interaction and gamification approaches.

SatisFactory will integrate novel concepts to the factory processes enhancing productivity through increased engagement of workers in the processes and through the stimulation of collaboration. To this end, user experience and gamification approaches will be developed, along with the introduction of a social collaboration platform, in which workers may exchange work knowledge / experiences / practices.

Objective 3: Real-time knowledge-sharing and AR-based collaboration and training services.

SatisFactory will create a knowledge base for the training of employees, along with the development of augmented reality (AR) technologies for delivering interactive training services, within an attractive ambient environment.

Objective 4: Improved shop floor feedback and decision making for gains in productivity, workers wellbeing and comfort.

SatisFactory will implement a decision-making system, which will be able to combine corroborating sources of evidence in terms of real-time data coming from the shop floor and aggregate dynamic information from production activities and critical human-centric and machinery related operations. It could offer feedback to the shop floor in terms of actionable knowledge and recommendations, including maintenance operations and schedules, utilizing AR and visual analytics technologies.

Objective 5: Adaptive and augmented interfaces for collaboration, knowledge sharing and real time support.

SatisFactory will enable real-time communication of information and knowledge among factory actors, either at their workplaces or on the move, using situated embodied interaction technologies enabled by wearable, adaptive and context-aware embedded devices and AR enabled glasses.

Objective 6: Deployment and Evaluation of the solution to large-scale Industrial Facilities from the Automotive and Energy factory domains.

SatisFactory will deploy and evaluate software and hardware products and the entire system to a pre-trial industrial lab (CERTH), and to two large-scale industrial facilities (COMAU with 23 different operative centres, 15 manufacturing plants, and 3 research and development centres in 6 EU Member States and throughout the world, and SUNLIGHT with 2 plants and 12 production/assembly lines).

SatisFactory SELECTED PILOT SITES

In order to test the deployment of the final system and measure the direct effects of SatisFactory developments in real world applications, two real-life industrial environments are selected (COMAU, SUNLIGHT) in the framework of SatisFactory, and one Industrial Lab Use Case (CERTH).

Application Scenarios/Use Cases and Pilot Trials for Evaluation of the envisaged solutions

SatisFactory will be validated in a series of scenarios and use cases designed to cover the most important aspects of the system and be possible to realize within the running period of the project. The following use cases show the possibilities of the proposed framework and they will form the basis for the development of SatisFactory.

1. Increase attractiveness of the Industrial Environment

One main disadvantage of industrial environments that discourages people from seeking a career in this field is the usual unattractiveness of the workplace in factories. Industrial workers usually have to deal with simple displays with minimum informational content and use difficult to handle and dangerous machinery. In addition, some types of work are mainly focused on the repetition of a task that can be both physically and mentally exhausting. Customisable augmented reality tools and functionalities will give to the employees the ability to control some aspects of his view of the working environment.

2. Communication platform for increased interaction between employees

One fundamental drawback of most industrial environments is that they do not allow easy communication and interaction of employees, especially on work related issues. An employee knows that he/she will have to stop his work and maybe step away from his/her workstation in order to ask for advice from a co-worker who will also have to be interrupted and maybe walk back to the first work station to check the problem of situation. In order to address this issue SatisFactory will realise a communication platform which will be augmented with attractive presentation and monitoring equipment allowing in this way employees to ask for advice instantly presenting their problem through a small camera attached on their HMDs and get feedback directly from someone with more experience, or maybe discuss an idea for a specific problem and work together for an innovative solution that could be adopted by the factory.

3. Continuous training and education of employees for the adaptation of the factory to new market requirements

In order to cope with the constantly and continuously changing market that drives industry, production lines nowadays have to be highly flexible supported by mechanisms for fast training of employees. Satisfactory will address this issue based on the dynamically expanding and semantically enhanced knowledge database. Algorithmic tools for object and task recognition supported by augmented reality will form the basis for employee training on-the-job without the need of the continuous attention of an educator. Easy and direct instruction will appear on the HMDs of trainees describing the next step to be performed. The direct communication will be also available when needed through the previous described communication platform.

4. Support of employees on the field with personalised dynamic information

One of the most useful SatisFactory components in terms of increased productivity but also safety and ergonomics will be a system supporting employees on-the-job without interruptions of difficult

methodologies. One example can be the real time information of the user about work related issues or dangers in his environment e.g. time for a component to arrive in the workstation or indication on a pipe of high temperature. In order to increase productivity and efficiently control the scheduling of the tasks of employees, instructions can be directly communicated to the employees informing them about what should be their next focus and how to manage timing related issues.

5. Real-Time Response of the manufacturing facilities to previously unavailable context-aware information

SatisFactory is promising to provide additional sources of information to this mechanism extending its possible applications. An indicative example could be the complete-shut down of a workstation when an unusual or dangerous incident occurs such as the fall of its operator.

PARTICIPANT SELECTION

All involved personnel working in the aforementioned selected pilot sites have already been notified on the project's objectives and the objective of the interviews and the extraction procedures that will take place during the pilots and have given their preliminary consent in participating in the pilot procedures. All people will be contacted again before the actual pilot preparation phase and will be asked to sign an appropriate consent form, verifying their participation.

DURATION

The total duration of the project's interviews will be one month in total, starting in March 2015. Within this period, the initial preparations for the interview will take place towards analysing the material gathered during the interviews. Due to limited time availability the interviews will be performed when the involved personnel will be available. Therefore, the actual duration of the interview may vary in each selected pilot site (COMAU, SUNLIGHT, CERTH).

ETHICS AND DEONTOLOGY

Regarding the acquisition and storage of human related information, the SatisFactory project has followed the appropriate ethics guidelines. These guidelines aim at preserving the privacy of the user, protecting his/her private data and limiting the risk of interception to the minimum. The integrity of the information is important for the project, and thus the following requirements have been fulfilled:

1. The researcher of the interview will inform the participants with clarity about the procedure of the interviews and the objectives of the data storage and analysis that will results from the analysis of the interview.
2. No sensitive personal data are collected. In no case more personal data will be collected than the necessary ones.
3. A data minimization policy will be adopted at all levels of the project and will be supervised by the ethical/privacy component of the project. This will ensure that no data which are not strictly necessary to the completion of the current study will be collected.
4. No data will be collected without the explicit consent of the individuals.

5. Participants will have the right to access their personal data as well as to their extracted profiling parameters.
6. The user will participate to the study, only after he/she has read, accepted and signed the consent form.
7. Participants will be able to quit the interview at any point, if they wish, without any consequences. He/she can exercise his/her right to access and delete his/her data at any moment.

Consent to Participate in Research Interviews

Procedures

If you agree to participate in this research study, an interview will be conducted with you at a time and location of your availability. The interview will involve questions about the daily operations and your collaboration with the other co-workers. It should last about two (2) hours. With your permission, I will audiotape and take notes during the interview. The recording is to accurately record the information you provide, and will be used for transcription purposes only. If you choose not to be audiotaped, I will take notes instead. If you agree to being audiotaped but feel uncomfortable at any time during the interview, the recorder can be turned off at your request. Or if you don't wish to continue, you can stop the interview at any time.

One interview is expected to be conducted. However, follow-ups may be needed for added clarification. If so, I will contact you by mail/phone to request this.

Confidentiality

Your data will be handled as confidentially as possible and will be pseudo-anonymized. If results of this study are published or presented, individual names and other personally identifiable information will not be used. When the research is completed, the audio related material will be deleted. The same measures described above will be taken to protect confidentiality of this study data.

Rights

Participation in research is completely voluntary. You are free to decline to take part in the project. You can decline to answer any questions and are free to stop taking part in the project at any time. Whether or not you choose to participate in the research and whether or not you choose to answer a question or continue participating in the project, there will be no penalty to you or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled.

Questions

If you have any questions about this research, please feel free to contact me. I can be reached at [phone number] or [email address].

CONSENT

I have read the institutes policies regarding the use of human participants and agree to abide by them. I am also familiar with the ethical principles with regard to human participants and the data protection Act. I further agree to submit any significant changes in procedures for additional review.

A copy of this consent will be available upon request.

If you wish to participate in this study, please sign and date below.

Participant:

Name of Participant Signature Date

Researcher:

Name of Researcher Signature Date

ANNEX 6 – ISSUES FROM JIRA DATABASE

Req. #1	SAFA-4		
The HMIs of the platform shall be attractive and easy to use			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The HMIs that will be created within the SatisFactory project must be user friendly in order to be easy to use from any actor who is involved with the project.		
Req. #2	SAFA-13		
The tools and applications must be 24/7 operational			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	CPERI is operating 24h each day, so all the tools and applications that will be installed at the shop floor must be continuously operational		
Req. #3	SAFA-17		
The tools shall be able to successfully exchange data with the existing infrastructure at the shop floors			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	SatisFactory platform will enhance the existing platforms at the shop floors in order to offer to the actors a better way to perform some of their activities		
Req. #4	SAFA-18		
SatisFactory tools shall give detailed description of selected maintenance actions			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Maintenance procedures will be recorded in order to be available to actors when necessary. They could be access via a tablet or a pc and actors will be guided how to perform the specific action		
Req. #5	SAFA-19		
The platform will include a personal protection equipment usage reminder			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	All actions within the shop floor must be performed with the necessary safety		

	measures. Thus, the system will remind the actor which measures must be used according to the performed action		
Req. #6	SAFA-24		
SatisFactory components must have a successful and continuous data exchange with CIDEM			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Blocker
Description:	All information must be passed through and stored at the Common Information Data Exchange Model - CIDEM. SatisFactory components must be able to successfully connect and exchange data with CIDEM		
Req. #7	SAFA-27		
Accurate detection of incidents			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	The SatisFactory tools shall be able to detect incidents which might be potential problems at the shop floors. The incident detection algorithms will be developed utilizing privacy preserving sensors and mechanisms.		
Req. #8	SAFA-31		
Successful integration of all heterogeneous devices of the shop floors			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	<p>SatisFactory provides a reference implementation for the integration of devices from the physical world, simplifying technological-specific exposing to the platform, including available resources and capabilities. Device Manager is a set of components developed on the basis of specific technologies to be adapted and fulfilling the following functionalities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of technology-dependant APIs or protocols to handle specific IoT physical objects. • Provisioning, over available networks and appropriate protocols (MQTT, REST, Web Services), actual devices data and measurements. • Devices presence management and device resources availability propagation at middleware level (LinkSmart Resource Catalogue). 		
Req. #9	SAFA-32		
Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) shall be provided to the workers			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Blocker
Description:	The platform that will be developed must be able to support the operators in accessing information and documents regarding Standard Operating Procedures		

	(SOP) in order to assist them in their job at the shop floor		
Req. #10	SAFA-33		
The platform of SatisFactory must enhance remote support and maintenance for the shop floors			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	The platform of SatisFactory must have an application which supports remote production support and remote maintenance in cases where no available technicians are at the point of a malfunction		
Req. #11	SAFA-34		
The system shall be able to monitoring actors through privacy preserving sensors			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	Innovative sensing and actuating technologies (IoT) offer a good basis for ergonomics parameters real-time monitoring of the actors at the shop floor (e.g. accelerations, number of repetitive operations performed, strength required in specific operations, etc.)		
Req. #12	SAFA-37		
The platform should present training procedures through multimedia content			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Blocker
Description:	All involved actors will have the opportunity to receive training through an innovative training environment that allows multimedia training procedures		
Req. #13	SAFA-40		
Depending on the SOP, some steps of the training activity shall be automatically verified			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	Depending on the SOP, some steps of the training activity should be automatically detected and verified, in order to proceed to the next step.		
Req. #14	SAFA-41		
All shop floor data must be stored in a common database			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	There are many devices and applications that will produce data or need data. In order to avoid conflicts, errors and interruptions of the normal status of the platform, all data must be stored in a common database and be accessible from all involved tools		

SATISFACTORY

	and applications. Middleware has the role of this common database.		
Req. #15	SAFA-55		
The system shall be able to detect both pro-active and re-active incidents at the shop floor			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	The Incident Detection Engine will support the safety and comfort of workers by detecting and recognizing the incidents (both proactive and reactive) in the shop-floor. It will be able to detect all incidents occurred in the shop-floor and eliminate potential false positives and true negatives.		
Req. #16	SAFA-58		
The AR components of SatisFactory must have continuous access to the database			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Blocker
Description:	The Augmented Reality (AR) components will use information related to specific actions for delivering interactive training services. This information will be coming from the database of the project (middleware)		
Req. #17	SAFA-59		
The platform shall support social communication between actors			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Blocker
Description:	Since there is a need for knowledge creation, sharing and access (e.g. visualization) technologies as well as the representation of knowledge in order to provide the necessary incentives to the actors, are involved in the production processes. The creation of this level of data will take into account the different devices that can be adopted and be part of the HMIs that will be created.		
Req. #18	SAFA-62		
Gamification tools will be interactive with the actors			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	The platform will include gamification tools which will be interactive with the actors and make the shop floors more attractive.		
Req. #19	SAFA-65		
AR tools will have the ability to interpret the displaying operating procedures			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Blocker

Description:	Tool, belonging to the AR platform, will have the ability to interpret the original operating procedures by providing a useful formalism specific to their management at run-time		
Req. #20	SAFA-66		
Multi-Layered Description of Operating Procedures (OP-MLD) Real-time Ready			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	Tool, belonging to the AR platform, will allow translating the original operating procedures in a characteristic "multi-level description". Each level will include a specific way to describe each step of the procedure (e.g. by images, by text messages, by 3D animations, etc.).		
Req. #21	SAFA-67		
The platform will allow uncoupling of Multi-Layered Description of operating procedures and their Interactive Real-time Visualization			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Nice to have
Description:	Tools, belonging to the platform of AR, will allow to download all and only the descriptive layers of an operating procedure, in order to allow the use them according to the choices of the operator and/or to the possibility of used physical devices.		
Req. #22	SAFA-69		
The symbols/terminology of the data presented on the glasses must be effective and easy to understand			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Minor
Description:	There will be a definition of error / safety information like icon menu dedicated to the worker that will be presented on the glasses.		
Req. #23	SAFA-73		
Continuous and successful data transfer between glasses and the database of each shop floor			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	The data transfer between glasses and the database of each shop floor has to be continuous in order for the glasses to be able to provide the appropriate information to the actors.		
Req. #24	SAFA-75		
The frame of the glasses shall be optimal for the workers			

Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Minor
Description:	Glasses form-factor/frame has to be defined.		
Req. #25	SAFA-76		
Real time and continuous monitoring of battery cell temperature during the procedure of Jar formation			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	The battery cells' temperature should be monitored continuously. This will increase the safety level and the operators will be focused only at the formation process.		
Req. #26	SAFA-79		
Real-time incident detection during Jar formation of batteries' cells			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The incident performed during the Jar formation of batteries' cell should be detected at real-time.		
Req. #27	SAFA-93		
Alarms shall be accompanied with a description			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	There are different alarms at frequent times and it is not always clear how to behave for a particular alarm.		
Req. #28	SAFA-101		
Different opinions shall be exchanged during the operation of a task			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	This is desired in case of meeting with problems. Spontaneously and directly asking co-workers for help was requested in the interviews.		
Req. #29	SAFA-105		
The system shall provide means of submitting suggestions for improvements available, in order to contribute to modernisation and overall improvement of working conditions			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	A working process for workers suggesting improvements is helpful for the overall process of the factory (benefit from management point of view). At the same time, workers benefit from it as they feel heard, involved and valuable, also feeling a kind of power to change something. Additionally such suggestions for improvement process can be rewarded separately. In general, it must be assured that the workers		

	know how to provide suggestions.		
Req. #30	SAFA-107		
The system shall utilize skills and capabilities of the workers available for optimal work assignment			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	Every individual worker fits better to some workplaces and worse to other workplaces and tasks. Thus, the supervisor & the HR Re-adaptation tool will optimally distribute tasks.		
Req. #31	SAFA-108		
The system shall improve teamwork through optimal task allocation			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	It is usually not possible to distribute work in a way that everybody's personal goals are fulfilled. The goal is to optimize teamwork and not to fulfil personal goals.		
Req. #32	SAFA-117		
The system shall support inter-change of best practices between departments and units			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Minor
Description:	The knowledge exchange between departments and unit can be less intensive than within a unit. Other units can benefit from best practices as well. Means to transfer descriptions of best practices between departments and units is provided.		
Req. #33	SAFA-118		
The product shall provide means to teach co-workers			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Teaching co-workers is considered valuable for teacher and learner.		
Req. #34	SAFA-120		
The communication product shall be open for non-work related content			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Minor
Description:	In order to boost teamwork, motivation, interaction and satisfaction, communication system shall not be restricted to work related content.		
Req. #35	SAFA-131		
Competition shall be informal and friendly			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major

Description:	Competing with others is a motivator for doing better work. However, if it is performed too dogged and fussy, it can lead to demotivation as well.		
Req. #36	SAFA-132		
The product shall not restrict workers' autonomy			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Workers have a level of autonomy that they don't want to be curbed.		
Req. #37	SAFA-133		
The system shall have access to the most recent work schedules			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Work plan and schedule changes occur frequently (several times a week), so the system has always access to the most recent work schedules.		
Req. #38	SAFA-134		
The system shall be able to be adapted to different shifts			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Sunlight is working in two shifts with weekly rotation.		
Req. #39	SAFA-135		
The system shall not influence workers' carefulness			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	It is easy to hurt yourself if you don't watch what you are doing		
Req. #40	SAFA-136		
The system shall be applicable when workers wear a mask			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The system will be operational in cases where workers wear masks.		
Req. #41	SAFA-137		
Support flexible deviations from plan			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Work timings and breaks are flexibly and spontaneously adapted when the situation		

	requires it.		
Req. #42	SAFA-140		
Support mobile users			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Most workers at the shopfloor don't have a fixed location like an office and they change their place of work often.		
Req. #43	SAFA-143		
Support feedback answers on suggestions for improvement			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	It is not always clear to workers what happens to their suggestions for improvement, i.e. they just see that a suggestions is not applied but do not know if the suggestion has reached the ear of the management or if it was rejected and for which reason.		
Req. #44	SAFA-146		
Release answers/feedback on suggestions for improvements to operators			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	If workers just see that their suggestions for improvement are not applied without knowing the reason, they get demotivated.		
Req. #45	SAFA-148		
Human-Resources toolkit shall efficient manage idle times			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	<p>"Operators can have idle times during which they could do other things. Since it is not clear how long a particular idle time lasts, it is not possible to do other things and be back in time when the actual work continues.</p> <p>Doing other things contributes to diversity at work, which in turn contributes to satisfaction at work."</p>		
Req. #46	SAFA-149		
The system should be able to manage all the open tasks			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	Operators can take over some tasks at idle times. For this, they need to know which tasks are open or where help is needed.		
Req. #47	SAFA-154		
Continuous access to training procedures			

Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	You forget tasks that you do not do often.		
Req. #48	SAFA-171		
All tasks should have priority and criticality ranks			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	A great motivator for workers is the feeling that the work they do is a highly important contribution to the overall production process. The user interviews at Sunlight revealed that the awareness that the working step the workers are involved in is an important one, makes them feel more motivated and satisfied at work. Therefore, the importance of the particular work step needs to be made clear for the worker conducting that step.		
Req. #49	SAFA-172		
The system shall be able to combine the heterogeneous acquired data from the shop floor			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Minor
Description:	Cooperative data acquisition approaches can assist obtaining a broader spectrum of information from the shop-floor and eventually improve the context extraction process.		
Req. #50	SAFA-174		
Continuous update of the operators' skills			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	Operators like to train others (it is a motivator) and they have expertise in special tasks or topics where they can train. This can be "advertised" so that other trainees or operators who search for training on those tasks or topics can approach them.		
Req. #51	SAFA-176		
The system shall provide efficient means for instructing workers on the necessary assembly parts of a battery belonging to an order and necessary actions at each step of the assembly procedure			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	Currently, the operator responsible for the first step of the traction battery assembly process at Sunlight gets a printed list of articles. The articles in the list are represented by figures (numbers). The worker needs to manually compare the number in the list to each of the articles physically present on the shop-floor till the particular article has been found. This procedure is quite tiresome and boring. It could be made more efficient and even maybe fun.		

Req. #52	SAFA-178		
Installation and troubleshooting of the system shall not require training beyond IT network administration and maintenance			
Type:	Deployment Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	All SatisFactory components should be easily installed and deployed without special IT knowledge.		
Req. #53	SAFA-181		
No frequencies, physical media, and protocols will be used for communication that interfere with existing communication systems at the factory			
Type:	Deployment Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	All frequencies, physical media, and protocols that will be utilized by the SatisFactory components will not affect the already installed systems at the shop-floor.		
Req. #54	SAFA-184		
The connectors, screws, and other electromechanical elements of the system shall match with the standard types used in the country where the factory is located			
Type:	Deployment Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	All equipment that will be utilized by SatisFactory components should be compatible with the standard used in the country where pilot site exists.		
Req. #55	SAFA-186		
The measurement units for the dimensions of the parts of the system shall match the units common in the deployment country.			
Type:	Deployment Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The measurement units should match to the common units deployed in the shop-floor country.		
Req. #56	SAFA-187		
Measurements, events, logs, and all shop floor dynamic shall be in the time zone of the deployment country			
Type:	Deployment Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The time zone that will be utilized by the SatisFactory components should be the		

	shop-floor's country time zone.		
Req. #57	SAFA-189		
HMI tool (on Mobile device) could be used to take photos from the working area			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Nice to have
Description:	The HMI tool will be able to take a photo of the area (process line) that was repaired and store it at the respective task (as declared at the iDSS-CMMS environment) in order to able to retrieve the useful information for the next time that the similar problem will occur.		
Req. #58	SAFA-192		
Association of the workers' names with their suggestions			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	Workers are encouraged to make suggestions to improve the existing process or even come up with new ideas. Some workers want to take credit for their suggestions by putting their name on it. According to them, they should be able to leave their name or identity behind so that they can claim rewards for it later.		
Req. #59	SAFA-193		
Time duration availability of the suggestions			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	"The user needs to know how long the suggestion has already been there, in order to evaluate possible next steps.		
Req. #60	SAFA-197		
UIs shall be in the formal language of the deployment country			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The UIs should be in the native language of the employees so that it is easier for them to understand the terms used.		
Req. #61	SAFA-198		
All UI interaction parts should be clearly visible			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The button should have clear text. Clear and easily understandable terms should be used to describe the purpose of that button.		

Req. #62	SAFA-200		
The UIs should be user-friendly			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	"<" back button should be better visible. At least there should be more space between the title of the category and the arrow		
Req. #63	SAFA-202		
Suggestions will be sorted by submission date			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Suggestions sorted by submission date associates a meaning to the way suggestions are being displayed. The latest suggestions should be displayed first.		
Req. #64	SAFA-203		
Suggestions filtering support			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	There can be different kinds of filtering and summarising the suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show all accepted • Show all rejected 		
Req. #65	SAFA-204		
Personal statistics available to the users			
Type:	User Need	Priority:	Major
Description:	With the badge there will be possible to see your own statistics, and prove that this accepted suggestions are yours.		
Req. #66	SAFA-205		
Evaluation of a contribution will support point scale			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	A point scale for the evaluation of a contribution could be used, in order to assess the importance of the contribution. A more important contribution gets more points.		
Req. #67	SAFA-206		
The product shall keep the prize detail separate from the system			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major

Description:	The prize or award details associated with the contributions should be stored separately.		
Req. #68	SAFA-207		
Suggestions system should support suggestion categories			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The suggestions are assigned to different categories depending on their relevancy. These categories are predefined and are to be provided by the factory management.		
Req. #69	SAFA-208		
Open suggestions shall be sent to the decision makers			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Decision makers should be notified periodically about open suggestions that they need to decide upon.		
Req. #70	SAFA-211		
The suggestion submission form shall be in similar format as the preexisting manual system			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	A manual system to submit suggestions for improvement already exists. The form to submit a suggestion in the suggestions platform should have the same format.		
Req. #71	SAFA-215		
Gamification must be presented in several subcomponents of satisfactory			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Gamification should not only be present just as a separate system but it should be present in several subcomponents of satisfactory.		
Req. #72	SAFA-217		
The gamification framework must support PBL			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Points, badges and leaderboards (PBL) are some of the most effective game elements in gamification. The gamification framework should support these elements.		
Req. #73	SAFA-218		

No participant of the gamification shall be exposed as looser			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The gamification framework shall ensure that no participant is exposed as a looser.		
Req. #74	SAFA-220		
Other Satisfactory components shall submit points of participants to the gamification framework			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The subcomponents of the satisfactory should be able to submit points of participants based on the tasks they perform.		
Req. #75	SAFA-221		
The gamification framework should allow workers to participate individually as well as in teams			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The participants should be allowed to take part on their own or in the forms of teams.		
Req. #76	SAFA-222		
All urgent tasks shall be properly allocated to the employees			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The HR workload balancing component is able to assign not planned arriving tasks to the most appropriate employees by taking into account multiple criteria (task priority, employee's workload etc.). These tasks are usually of high importance/priority and must be started as soon as possible, even in the case where all the candidate employees are busy. The current schedule of each employee capable of performing the task along with static information about employees (e.g. Trade) shall be used as input. Furthermore, the following parameters about an arriving task should be known: Weight priority, estimated duration, required employee trade and required number of employees.		
Req. #77	SAFA-223		
Current location of employee shall be taken into account by the RA & HR workload balancing tool			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	In case of an arrival of an urgent task, the current location of each candidate employee (e.g. expressed as X, Y coordinates) can be taken into account in order to assign the task to the nearest employee. The arriving task's location must be known		

	as well in order to compute the distance.		
Req. #78	SAFA-224		
The system should be able to interface existing measurement tools and infrastructure			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	The system should be able to interact with existing measurement tools in order to acquire measurements.		
Req. #79	SAFA-225		
All historical data from the shop-floor shall be available through CIDEM			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Critical
Description:	All SatisFactory components will be able to retrieve shop-floor historical information through CIDEM		
Req. #80	SAFA-226		
All information exchanged and stored within SatisFactory components shall be in a common format understandable from all components			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Blocker
Description:	All information exchanged within SatisFactory components shall be in a common format understandable from all components.		
Req. #81	SAFA-227		
Timely workers notification in case of an alarm			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	Timely workers notification in case of an alarm		
Req. #82	SAFA-228		
The UI shall provide maps visualization for a more concrete understanding			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Nice to have
Description:	The UI shall provide maps visualization, so as workers understand the location of the incident, alarm or any other information visualized at the platform.		
Req. #83	SAFA-229		
The messages provided by the system shall be clear and easy to understand			
Type:	Volere	Priority:	Major

	Requirement		
Description:	The messages provided by the system shall be clear and easy to understand.		
Req. #84	SAFA-230		
The SatisFactory components shall be able to store and retrieve large amounts of data			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	The SatisFactory components shall be able to store and retrieve large amounts of data.		
Req. #85	SAFA-231		
In case one or more components are not reachable on the network, the system shall be able to manage the whole operation without them and their data			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	In case one or more components are not reachable on the network, the system shall be able to manage the whole operation without them and their data		
Req. #86	SAFA-232		
Communication among SatisFactory components will be platform independent			
Type:	Volere Requirement	Priority:	Major
Description:	All SatisFactory components will be able to communicate among each other (especially with Middleware and CIDEM). The communication of the components will be platform independent and will not be affected by the operating system or the application that have been developed.		